

1 **CO elimination processes over promoter-free hydroxyapatite supported**
2 **palladium catalysts**

3
4
5 Zouhair Boukha, José L. Ayastuy, Juan R. González-Velasco,

6 Miguel A. Gutiérrez-Ortiz

7
8 Chemical Technologies for Environmental Sustainability Group,

9 Department of Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Science and Technology,

10 University of The Basque Country UPV/EHU,

11 P.O. Box 644, E-48080 Bilbao, Spain

12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21 *Corresponding author: Zouhair Boukha

22 Phone: +34 946015502

23 Fax: +34 946013500

24 E-mail address: zouhair.boukha@ehu.eus

25 **Abstract**

26

27 The catalytic performance of synthesised calcium-deficient hydroxyapatite supported Pd
28 catalysts are examined for various CO elimination processes, namely CO total
29 oxidation, CO preferential oxidation and water gas shift reactions. The prepared
30 samples loaded with different amounts of palladium (0.5-2%) are thoroughly
31 characterised by a wide number of analytical techniques including N₂ physisorption,
32 XRD, H₂-TPR, TEM, CO-TPD, H₂ chemisorption, OSCC and OSC techniques. The
33 characterisation results show that, besides an incorporation of 0.3 wt% Pd into
34 hydroxyapatite structure, on the Pd(0.5)/HAP sample, small Pd particle sizes (7.6 nm)
35 are deposited on the HAP support surface presenting relatively high dispersion (19%).
36 The OSCC and OSC studies show that the highly dispersed Pd species lying on the
37 HAP surface present high reducibility and high oxygen mobility.

38 In the three investigated CO elimination processes the Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst proves to
39 be highly active and exhibits higher stability compared to that of the Pd(1)/HAP and
40 Pd(2)/HAP catalysts. The catalytic performance of the series of the catalysts
41 demonstrates their structure-sensitivity in the investigated processes. The latter are
42 remarkably enhanced in the presence of small Pd particle sizes which provide high
43 reducibility and high oxygen storage capacity. Moreover, the performances of the
44 Pd/HAP catalysts evidence the potential of HAP support as promising alternative to
45 those reported in the available literature.

46

47 *Keywords:* Hydroxyapatite, Pd particle size, OSC, OSCC, COPROX, WGS.

48

49

50 **1. Introduction**

51 The use of hydrogen as fuel is a promising alternative to produce clean and efficient
52 energy [1,2]. However, due to its production mainly via the reforming of hydrocarbons
53 its purification is necessary to eliminate the traces of CO in the hydrogen stream;
54 especially, when the posterior use can only tolerate very low concentration of CO (<
55 100 ppm) as in the case of the polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cell (PEMFC)
56 applications. For this purpose, the water gas shift reaction (WGSR) and CO preferential
57 oxidation (COPROX) processes are applied as post-reforming stages for removing most
58 of the CO and producing additional H₂.

59 Generally, catalysts for total CO oxidation (COTOX) consist of transition metal oxides
60 (Cu, Co and Mn) and supported noble metal (Pt, Pd, Au and Ru) catalysts [1-4]. Despite
61 the economical consideration that motivates their use the activity of transition metals is
62 still relatively low compared to the promoted noble metals. Moreover, the former are
63 sensitive to H₂O [5]. Among the noble metal catalysts, Pd-based catalysts have attracted
64 a considerable attention during the past several decades.

65 Usually, the Pd active phases are supported on active (such as CeO₂, MnO_x, TiO₂ and
66 Fe₂O₃) or inert (such as Al₂O₃ graphene and SiO₂) metal oxides presenting relatively
67 high specific surface area [5-14]. Liu et al. [8] studied the role of FeO_x support for
68 oxygen supply, compared to alumina support, during CO oxidation reaction. They
69 found that CO oxidation over Pd/FeO_x occurs on two adjacent active sites (Pd for CO
70 and FeO_x for oxygen) with low activation energy (34 kJ mol⁻¹), compared to that
71 obtained on Pd/Al₂O₃ catalyst (71 kJ mol⁻¹), which accounts for the dramatic difference
72 in activity from Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃ supported Pd. Furthermore, the effect of some
73 additives, such as ceria, cobalt, zinc and alkaline earth metals as promoters to enhance
74 the activity of Pd catalysts, has been extensively studied [11-13]. The main objectives

75 are the stabilization of the Pd species structures and the enhancement of the redox
76 properties of the surface active phases which play an important role in the catalytic
77 properties of these systems in CO oxidation.

78 Nevertheless, Pd catalysts show very low activity and selectivity in the presence of
79 hydrogen (COPROX process) [15-17]. The oxidation of H₂ appeared to be greatly
80 favoured at the expense of CO oxidation. Oh et al. [15] associated this low COPROX
81 activity, over their Pd/Al₂O₃ catalysts, with the formation of PdO_x species which are
82 very active in hydrogen oxidation. Also, Pozdnyakova et al. [16] observed a poor
83 activity on Pd catalysts, even with reducible support (CeO₂). They claimed that, in the
84 presence of hydrogen, formation of Pd β-hydride greatly suppressed the possibility of
85 CO oxidation, because oxygen from both gas-phase and support sites (and also from
86 PdO_x) reacts rapidly with H₂ to form water, which desorbs easily.

87 On the other hand, Pd catalysts supported on various supports were also studied in WGS
88 reaction [18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23]. In this case, reducible supports (CeO₂, TiO₂, Fe₂O₃ and
89 Co₂O₃) are frequently used. According to Sekine et al. [19] despite their lower initial
90 activity the Pd/LaCoO₃ catalysts exhibit superior stability compared to Pt/LaCoO₃
91 catalysts. They also reported that Pd-Pt/LaCoO₃ catalyst presents higher activity and
92 stability than that of a commercially available catalyst (Cu-ZnO). Hilaire et al. [20]
93 showed that Pd/ceria exhibited much higher activities than either ceria alone or
94 Pd/silica, demonstrating a cooperative effect between Pd and ceria. Moreover, they
95 proposed a mechanism involving a redox process which consists on the oxidation of
96 reduced ceria by water and then transferring oxygen to the active metal to react with
97 adsorbed CO. In their study on the Pd model catalysts, Pd/Al₂O₃ and Pd/CZ, Lupescu et
98 al. [23] concluded that to prolong the performance throughout the life of the catalyst a

99 relatively high dispersion of Pd should be maintained. This also implies the importance
100 of the support applied to disperse the Pd species.

101 To resume, the applicability of Pd catalyst is a topic of high interest both scientifically
102 and technically. Various supports are used to disperse the Pd species and to generate
103 new interactions which promote their activity. In the present work, we study the
104 applicability of hydroxyapatite (HAP), $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$, as a porous support of the Pd
105 species for three CO elimination processes (COTOX, COPROX and WGS). Our interest
106 in this kind of materials is justified by the flexibility of its crystal structure and its high
107 ion-exchange ability which may lead to the speciation of the metal active phases [24-
108 26]. Moreover, HAP offers the possibility of tuning the surface chemical properties by
109 varying the calcium/phosphorus ratio [24-26]. These interesting characteristics confer to
110 HAP materials a large room for improvement in their catalytic activity and selectivity.
111 Though a number of studies dealing with hydroxyapatite as support are presently
112 available [24-26], to the best of our knowledge, the applications of the prepared
113 Pd(x)/hydroxyapatite in such reactions and our approach to explain their catalytic
114 behavior have not been yet investigated. Interesting conclusions have been drawn from
115 the correlation between the distribution of Pd active species and their performance in
116 the three investigated processes.

117

118 **2. Experimental**

119 **2.1. Preparation of the catalysts**

120 Calcium-deficient hydroxyapatite support (HAP), with Ca/P molar ratio equal to 1.50,
121 was synthesized adding drop wise a boiled aqueous solution of calcium nitrate to a
122 solution of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$. The precipitate was re-dissolved in a nitric acid solution and
123 neutralized with ammonia at pH 10. The resulting mixture was maintained under

124 stirring at 80 °C for 16 h. After filtration, the recovered solid was washed well with
125 purified water then dried at 120 °C and finally calcined at 500 °C for 4 h.

126 The Pd(x)/HAP catalysts were prepared by impregnation of the corresponding support
127 by tetraamminepalladium (II) chloride monohydrate where x is the Pd wt.% content
128 (Table 1). The prepared catalysts were calcined at 500°C (4 h). The activated samples
129 were obtained after a reduction under 20% H₂/He at 200 °C for 2 h followed by a
130 treatment at 500 °C in a flow of pure He.

131

132 **2.2. Characterisation techniques**

133 The volumetric N₂ adsorption at -196 °C was performed on an automatic apparatus
134 Micromeritics, model TRISTAR II 3020 apparatus. The pre-treatments applied to the
135 samples consisted of a cleaning, at 300 °C (overnight), under nitrogen flow. The
136 specific areas of the samples were determined in line with the standard BET procedure,
137 using nitrogen adsorption taken in the relative equilibrium pressure interval of 0.03-0.3.

138 X-ray diffraction (XRD) studies were conducted on a X'PERT-MPD X-ray
139 diffractometer with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) and Ni filter. The X-ray tube was
140 operated at 40 kV and 40 mA. The samples were scanned between 10° and 100° (2θ),
141 and the X-ray diffraction line positions were determined with a step size of 0.01° and a
142 counting time of 2.5 s per step. Phase identification was conducted by comparison with
143 JCPDS database cards.

144 The morphology, size and dispersion of the palladium particles lying on the reduced
145 Pd(x)/HAP surface were examined by transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The
146 TEM studies were performed on a Philips CM200 transmission electron microscope
147 equipped with LaB₆ filament operating at 200 kV and combined with X-ray energy
148 dispersive spectroscopy (X-EDS) techniques. The latter was used to confirm the

149 absence of chlorine phases from our samples surface. The average diameter of
150 palladium particles was obtained from the measurement of at least 300 particles using
151 ImageJ software. The corresponding values for palladium dispersion, D_{TEM} , and specific
152 palladium surface area were calculated according to a procedure previously described
153 by Borodzinski et al. [27].

154 The reducibility of the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts was examined by temperature-programmed
155 reduction (H_2 -TPR) on a Micromeritics AutoChem 2920 instrument equipped with a
156 thermal conductivity detector (TCD). Firstly, all the samples were pre-treated in an
157 oxygen stream ($5\% \text{O}_2/\text{He}$, $50 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$) at $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h and then cooled to $-30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in a
158 flow of He ($50 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$). The reducing gas was $5\% \text{H}_2/\text{Ar}$ with a flow rate of
159 $50 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$. The temperature range explored was from $-30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, with a
160 heating rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$. This temperature was maintained for 30 min. The produced
161 water was trapped in a cold trap, and the consumption of H_2 was quantitatively
162 measured by time integration of the H_2 -TPR profiles.

163 The H_2 chemisorption measurements were carried out on the same experimental setup,
164 used for H_2 -TPR experiments. The catalysts (80 mg) were submitted to a pre-reduction
165 at $200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (2 h) in a flow $5\% \text{H}_2/\text{Ar}$ ($50 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$) followed by a treatment with Ar (50
166 $\text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$) at 500°C . H_2 pulses ($5\% \text{H}_2/\text{Ar}$, loop volume: 0.5 cm^3) were then injected in
167 Ar carrier ($50 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$) over the sample, at $70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [28]. The Pd dispersion, D_{chem} ,
168 defined as the active metal fraction exposed ($D_{\text{chem}} = \text{Pd}_s / \text{Pd}_{\text{tot}}$) was determined on the
169 assumption of a unity adsorption stoichiometry ($\text{H}/\text{Pd}_s = 1$); where “ Pd_s ” represents the
170 surface Pd atoms and “ Pd_{tot} ” represents the total amounts of Pd. The mean diameter of
171 Pd particles was calculated, assuming that Pd particles have a spherical shape, from the
172 following expressions [27]:

173

174 i) For D_{chem} in the range 0.01-0.2: $d(\text{nm}) = 1.404/D_{\text{chem}}$ (1)

175 ii) For D_{chem} in the range 0.2-0.84: $d(\text{nm}) = 1.180/D_{\text{chem}}$ (2)

176 The temperature programmed desorption of CO studies (CO-TPD) were carried out on
177 the same experimental setup, used for H₂-TPR experiments, coupled to a MKS Cirrus
178 LM99 mass spectrometer. The catalysts were submitted to a pre-treatment consisting on
179 their reduction at 200 °C (2 h) in a flow 5% H₂/Ar (50 cm³ min⁻¹) followed by a
180 treatment with He (50 cm³ min⁻¹) at 500°C. The adsorption of CO was performed at -
181 120 °C in a flow of 5% CO/He (50 cm³ min⁻¹) for 1 h. After CO adsorption the samples
182 were treated with He for 1 h and heated at 10 °C min⁻¹ up to 500 °C in flowing He (50
183 cm³ min⁻¹). The MS signals (m/z = 28, 44 and 18) assigned to CO, CO₂ and H₂O,
184 respectively, were followed. Note that the quantification of CO amount was corrected
185 taking into account the contribution of the signal m/z:44.

186 The Oxygen Storage Complete Capacity (OSCC) and Oxygen Storage Capacity (OSC)
187 experiments at different temperatures (150°C, 200°C, 250°C, 300°C, 350°C and 400
188 °C) were carried out on the same experimental setup coupled to MKS Cirrus LM99
189 mass spectrometer. The catalysts (25 mg, 40-80 μm) were submitted to a reduction at
190 200 °C (2 h) in a flow 5% H₂/Ar followed by a treatment with He at 500°C. For the
191 OSCC measurements, the samples were submitted to ten O₂ pulses (5% O₂/He, loop
192 volume: 5 cm³), injected in He carrier, followed by ten CO pulses (5% CO/He, loop
193 volume: 5 cm³). The OSCC values were determined from the sum of the CO₂ amounts
194 formed after each CO pulse. After degas in a He flow OSC measurements were
195 performed on the same samples. The latter were submitted to six alternating series of
196 pulses (CO-O₂) where the OSC was determined as the average amount of the formed
197 CO₂ for each CO pulse.

198

199 2.3. Catalytic tests

200 The catalytic tests were performed, with flow/mass ratio of $1333 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1} \text{ g}^{-1}$, in a
201 tubular flow reactor operating at atmospheric pressure using 150 mg of the catalyst.
202 Prior to running the catalytic experiments, the catalysts were submitted to a pre-
203 treatment routine consisting on their reduction at $200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (2 h) in a flow $20\% \text{ H}_2/\text{He}$
204 followed by a treatment with He at 400°C . Three different feed gas mixtures with the
205 same oxygen excess ($\lambda = 2$ ($P_{\text{O}_2}/P_{\text{CO}} = 2$)) and balanced with He, to reach a total flow
206 rate of $200 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$, were used in each reaction as follows:

- 207 • 1% CO and 1% O₂ in COTOX reaction.
- 208 • 1% CO, 1% O₂ and 60% H₂ in COPROX reaction.
- 209 • 1% CO and 2% H₂O in WGS reaction.

210 The reaction products were continuously analysed by Gas Chromatograph (Agilent
211 Technologies 490 Micro GC) equipped with a TCD detector. Carbon monoxide
212 conversions (X_{CO}) and selectivity to CO₂ (S_{CO_2}) were calculated by using the inlet (F^{in})
213 and outlet (F^{out}) molar flow values of the two reactants (eqn. (3) and eqn. (4),
214 respectively):

$$X_{\text{CO}} (\%) = 100 \cdot \frac{F_{\text{CO}}^{\text{in}} - F_{\text{CO}}^{\text{out}}}{F_{\text{CO}}^{\text{in}}} \quad (3)$$

$$S_{\text{CO}_2} (\%) = 100 \cdot 0.5 \cdot \frac{F_{\text{CO}}^{\text{in}} - F_{\text{CO}}^{\text{out}}}{F_{\text{O}_2}^{\text{in}} - F_{\text{O}_2}^{\text{out}}} \quad (4)$$

215 Turnover frequency (TOF) values were calculated as the activity data per mole of active
216 surface palladium determined by H₂ chemisorption experiments [2-3]. In order to assure
217 differential reactor conditions the temperatures used for the calculations of turnover
218 frequency (TOF) for the three tested reactions over the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts
219 corresponded to low CO conversions (< 20%). The absence of heat and mass transfer
220 limitations were checked following the criterions described elsewhere [29].

221

222 **3. Results and discussion**

223 **3.1. Characterization of the samples**

224 **3.1.1. N₂-physorption (BET measurements)**

225 The textural properties of the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts were examined by nitrogen
226 adsorption-desorption measurements. The experimental N₂ physisorption isotherms for
227 the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts in their calcined and reduced forms (not shown) show that they
228 are characteristic of mesoporous materials exhibiting IV-type according to the IUPAC
229 classification. The specific surface area, pore volume and average pore size are shown
230 in Table1. Fig. 1S (Supporting information) shows the pore size distributions for all the
231 reduced catalysts. The pore size distribution corresponding to HAP support and the
232 Pd(x)/HAP catalysts show a broad unimodal distribution centred at approximately
233 32 nm (Fig. 1S). This distribution does not change with the introduction of palladium.
234 However, the addition of palladium (0.5-2%) to HAP produces a slight drop in its
235 specific surface area (up to 19%) and pore volume. For instance, the specific surface
236 area of the resultant catalysts significantly decreases from 52 m² g⁻¹ for the HAP bare
237 support to 48 m² g⁻¹ for the oxidised and 42-44 m² g⁻¹ for the reduced Pd(x)/HAP
238 catalysts. Table 1 also lists the textural data of the used catalysts in the COTOX,
239 COPROX and WGS reactions which will be commented below.

240

241 **3.1.2. X-ray diffraction (XRD)**

242 The Pd(x)/HAP samples were also characterised by means of X-ray powder diffraction
243 in order to investigate the effect of the Pd addition on their structural properties. Fig. 1a
244 displays the XR-diffractograms corresponding to the reduced Pd(x)/HAP and HAP bare
245 support samples. The patterns of the latter are characterised by the presence of the

246 maxima at $2\theta = 26.15^\circ, 32.06^\circ, 32.49^\circ, 33.19^\circ$ and 34.32° , among others. As expected,
247 these 2θ angles values are slightly higher than those corresponding to stoichiometric
248 hydroxyapatite used as reference (JCPDS 01-082-2956). This is because of the
249 synthesised support consists of a calcium-deficient hydroxyapatite with Ca/P molar
250 ratio equal to 1.50 (Table 1); lower than the 1.67 expected for a stoichiometric
251 hydroxyapatite ($\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$). In our previous study we explained this non-
252 stoichiometry by a loss of Ca^{2+} ions, which is corrected by insertion of H^+ ions at the
253 expense of hydroxyl groups to ensure electroneutrality [24]. Hence, the general formula
254 of these calcium deficient hydroxyapatite can be denoted as
255 $\text{Ca}_{10-z}(\text{HPO}_4)_z(\text{PO}_4)_{6-z}(\text{OH})_{2-z}$ where $0 < z \leq 1$.

256 On the other hand, it is difficult to evidence the presence of the Pd structure peaks on
257 the diffractograms of Pd(x)/HAP catalysts; especially, the diffraction peaks
258 corresponding to (111), (200), (220) and (311) planes which characterise the presence of
259 metallic palladium structure. This is may be due to the overlapping of the Pd peaks with
260 those of hydroxyapatite structure. Indeed, a comparison between the Pd(x)/HAP
261 samples shows that the peak at 40° is broader on the Pd(1)/HAP and Pd(2)/HAP
262 diffractograms compared to that of Pd(0.5)/HAP and HAP support, suggesting an
263 apparent overlapping of the peak corresponding to metallic Pd (111) with that
264 associated to hydroxyapatite (130).

265 Interestingly, the XRD patterns of the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts show a significant evolution
266 of the hydroxyapatite diffraction peaks which shift to lower angles with Pd loading
267 increasing. For instance, 2θ angle corresponding to (211) reticular plane shifts from
268 32.06° for the HAP sample to 31.93° and 31.89° for Pd(1)/HAP and Pd(2)/HAP
269 samples, respectively (Fig. 1b). These observations suggest that the presence of
270 palladium induces a modification of the cell parameters of the HAP structure. Table 2

271 lists the most important structure parameters in terms of the lattice parameters, “a” and
272 “c”, and unit cell volume (V). Values corresponding to stoichiometric HAP (Ca/P:1.67)
273 are also included for comparison. The reported data show that the lattice parameter “a”
274 increases with increasing the Pd content. Likewise, the lattice parameter “c” calculated
275 in all the Pd catalysts is higher than that of the HAP bare support. This increase in “a”
276 and “c” values with palladium addition induces an apparent increase in the unit cell
277 volume suggesting a progressive incorporation of Pd in the HAP crystal lattice. As the
278 ionic radius of the Pd²⁺ (100 pm) is smaller than that of Ca²⁺ (114 pm) the observed
279 expansion might be due to an incorporation of Pd²⁺ into the cationic vacant sites rather
280 than an ion-exchange process with Ca²⁺ sites.

281

282 **3.1.3. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)**

283 Hydroxyapatite-supported palladium samples, reduced at 200 °C, are investigated by
284 TEM techniques. Fig. 2 shows their corresponding TEM micrographs and particle size
285 distribution diagrams. Examination of the Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst reveals the presence of
286 quasi-spherical Pd particles which are homogeneously dispersed on the support surface.
287 Furthermore, the size distribution trace of these Pd particles consists of a narrow
288 unimodal distribution with an average size of 7.6 nm corresponding to dispersion value
289 of 19% (Table 2). This Pd dispersion value (19%) is consistent with those found by
290 Guadet et al. [30] in their Pd/Al₂O₃ and Pd/La-Al₂O₃ systems (17-25%) presenting
291 similar surface density of the Pd (1.2-1.6 μmol m⁻²). At high Pd loading the particle
292 sizes consist of a broader distribution with an average size of 13.1 nm for Pd(1)/HAP
293 and 16.3 nm for Pd(2)/HAP, with relatively lower dispersion (10.4% and 8.4%,
294 respectively) compared to the catalyst with the lowest Pd loading (Pd(0.5)/HAP).

295 On the other hand, the X-EDS analyses of the Pd(x)/HAP samples after their calcination at 500
296 °C followed by reduction at 200 °C confirm the absence of Cl species on the Pd(x)/HAP surface.
297

298 **3.1.4. H₂-TPR and H₂ chemisorption studies**

299 The H₂-TPR experiments were performed in order to determine the different Pd
300 reducible species present in the prepared Pd(x)/HAP catalysts (Fig. 3). The H₂-TPR
301 profiles included in Fig. 3 show typical spectra for oxidized Pd species consisting of a
302 reduction peak at 22 °C associated with the reduction of Pd oxides (Peak I) and a second
303 negative peak at 68 °C corresponding to palladium hydride (Pd-H) decomposition
304 leading to hydrogen release (Peak II). Generally, the latter could be formed at lower
305 temperatures equivalent to those corresponding to oxidized Pd species reduction [31-
306 33]. Table 3 reports quantitative data corresponding to the integration of the two
307 resulting peaks and the corresponding H₂(I)/Pd and H₂(II)/Pd molar ratios determined as
308 mole of consumed and released H₂ per mole of total palladium, respectively. Moreover,
309 taking into account the formation of Pd hydride concurrently with the reduction of
310 oxidized species of Pd the actual amounts of consumed H₂ for the reduction process
311 (H₂^(R)/Pd) is determined as the difference between the amounts of the consumed and the
312 released H₂ (H₂^(R)/Pd= H₂(I)/Pd - H₂(II)/Pd). For the Pd(0.5)/HAP sample, the
313 calculated H₂^(R)/Pd molar ratio is around 0.43 which is lower than that expected for the
314 reduction of stoichiometric palladium oxide (PdO). This result suggests a presence of a
315 fraction of Pd species which does not reduce in the TPR operating conditions (heating
316 in H₂/Ar at temperatures up to 600 °C). Similar conclusions can be extracted for the
317 Pd(1)/HAP and Pd(2)/HAP samples which also present low H₂^(R)/Pd ratios (0.69 and
318 0.85, respectively). Interestingly, for all the Pd(x)/HAP samples, an estimation of this
319 Pd non-reducible fraction show that it is around 0.29-0.31 wt% of the total weight of the
320 sample. This is a remarkable observation indicating that it represents an upper limit for

321 a certain interaction of Pd species with the HAP support which makes them non-
322 reducible (up to 600 °C). In agreement with the XRD results, which proposed a possible
323 incorporation of Pd into the hydroxyapatite network, we can conclude that the level of
324 such incorporation is limited to 0.3 wt% Pd.

325 Table 3 also lists the Pd dispersion, active Pd surface area and average particle size for
326 the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts as determined from the H₂ chemisorption measurements.
327 Interestingly, the three catalysts exhibit comparable active Pd surface area which is
328 around 0.42-0.47 m_{Pd}² g⁻¹ (Table 3). The comparison of the obtained results with those
329 obtained by TEM techniques shows slight differences in the case of the Pd(0.5)/HAP and
330 Pd(1)/HAP catalysts. By contrast, on the Pd(2)/HAP catalyst the Pd dispersion value
331 measured by H₂ chemisorption results significantly lower (5%) compared to that
332 determined by TEM techniques (8.4%). These observations suggested that, on the Pd-
333 rich catalyst a large fraction of Pd is not accessible to the gas phase.

334 On the other hand, in agreement with a number of earlier studies from the literature the
335 formation of palladium hydride depends on the palladium particle sizes [31-34]. In this
336 sense, it was reported that large Pd particles easily form Pd hydride whereas small Pd
337 particles partially inhibit its formation. According to the determined amounts of
338 released H₂ reported in Table 3 it can be concluded that small Pd particles are deposited
339 on the Pd(0.5)/HAP sample compared to those deposited on the higher Pd loadings
340 samples (1% and 2%). On the latter, the H₂(II)/Pd ratio corresponding to the integration
341 of the negative peak at 68 °C reach relatively higher values (0.11-0.15) which indicate
342 an initiation of the tridimensional growth of Pd particles. In this sense, Fig. 4 shows a
343 clear correlation between the amounts of released H₂ during the H₂-TPR experiments (at
344 68 °C) and the Pd particle sizes determined by TEM (Fig. 4a) and/or those determined
345 by H₂ chemisorptions (Fig. 4b).

346 3.1.5. CO-TPD study

347 The thermal stability of pre-adsorbed CO on the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts was investigated
348 by means of CO-TPD techniques. The TPD profiles of pre-adsorbed CO at -120 °C on
349 the reduced Pd(x)/HAP catalysts are presented in Fig. 5. Data corresponding to the HAP
350 bare support are also included for comparison. Generally, at low temperatures (< 100 °C)
351 the CO desorption peaks are associated with linearly bonded CO (weakly adsorbed CO
352 species) while the desorption peaks centred at high temperatures (> 200 °C) are
353 attributed to bridge-bonded CO (strongly adsorbed CO species) [35].

354 For all the analysed samples large amounts of CO are desorbed at low temperatures
355 which are related to linearly bonded CO (Fig. 5a). As reported in Table 3 the amount of
356 desorbed CO from the HAP, 397 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$, is much higher than those determined for the
357 three Pd catalysts (182-230 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$). It can also be observed that the amount of the
358 weakly adsorbed CO increases with the Pd loadings increase, 182 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ for
359 Pd(0.5)/HAP, 215 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ for Pd(1)/HAP and 230 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ for Pd(2)/HAP. This trend
360 suggests that the high dispersion of Pd tends to decrease the density of the weak-
361 strength adsorption sites of CO. However, the Pd(0.5)/HAP sample exclusively exhibits
362 additional CO desorption peak which occurs at temperature around 290 °C (Fig 5a).
363 This fraction, that represents 4% of the total amount of desorbed CO, can be associated
364 to the highly dispersed Pd species.

365 Fig. 5b displays the profiles of the formation/release of CO₂ during the CO-TPD
366 experiments. It should be noted that in addition to CO₂ formation small amount of H₂O
367 is observed in the desorbing gas (not shown), suggesting the occurrence of the water gas
368 shift reaction of the adsorbed CO with the surface hydroxyl groups of the support [35-
369 37]. On the HAP bare support the release of CO₂ starts around 180 °C which forms a
370 broad desorption peak presenting a maximum at 350 °C (Fig. 5b). By contrast, on the

371 Pd(x)/HAP catalysts the formation of CO₂ starts at relatively lower temperatures
372 (around 100 °C). Likewise, the position of the CO₂ peaks seems to shift toward low
373 temperatures compared with that of HAP. For instance, the Pd(1)/HAP and Pd(2)/HAP
374 samples exhibit a CO₂ production peak at 300 °C while the Pd(0.5)/HAP sample
375 exhibits two peaks at 200 °C and 300 °C. Table 3 also lists the total amounts of desorbed
376 CO₂ extracted from the integration of its corresponding peaks. It can be observed that
377 the addition of palladium onto the HAP surface dramatically increases the amount of the
378 desorbed CO₂. For instance, the surface density of CO₂ desorbed from the support,
379 0.8 μmol g_{cat}⁻¹, is much smaller than that determined for Pd(0.5)/HAP, 4 μmol g_{cat}⁻¹.
380 The latter also demonstrates that it bears more active sites associated with the
381 formation of CO₂ than the Pd(1)/HAP and Pd(2)/HAP catalysts (2.7-2.9 μmol g⁻¹). As
382 suggested by the TPD traces for the three Pd catalysts (Fig. 5b) the loss observed in the
383 density of these active sites observed upon increasing the palladium concentration may
384 be correlated with the disappearance of the CO₂ desorption peak at 200 °C, which can
385 be associated with the presence of highly dispersed Pd species.

386 These remarkable differences between the Pd(x)/HAP samples point out the effect of
387 the Pd dispersion on the amount, distribution and activity of the CO adsorption sites. In
388 this sense, the high dispersion of the Pd species decreases the density of the weak-
389 strength adsorption sites of CO and increases the density of strong adsorption sites by
390 providing extra active sites.

391

392 **3.1.6. OSCC and OSC studies**

393 The OSCC and OSC studies on the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts in the temperature range
394 between 150 °C and 400°C are summarized in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7. By means of OSCC
395 valuable information about the maximum reducibility of the catalysts can be gained

396 while the OSC results provide a quantification of the most reactive and available
397 oxygen atoms.

398 As reported in Fig. 6a and Fig. 6b negligible amounts of CO₂ are released before
399 200 °C on the HAP bare support. At higher temperatures, oxygen storage sites on the
400 surface may be accessed. As temperature increases, the OSC and OSCC increases
401 proceed via different pathways. OSC does not exceed 17 μmol_{CO2} g⁻¹ at 400 °C, Fig. 6b,
402 probably because it is limited by the most reactive species located at the support
403 surface. By contrast, much higher OSCC values are obtained in all the range of
404 investigated temperatures (Fig. 6b). For instance it reaches 123 μmol_{CO2} g⁻¹ at 400 °C.
405 This behavior, which represents the maximum reducibility, suggests that OSCC seems
406 to be controlled by a participation of bulk oxygen. Nevertheless, all the OSCC and OSC
407 values obtained on the HAP bare support, evidence its low activity compared to
408 reducible supports. For instance, at 250 °C the OSCC is around 15 μmol CO₂ g⁻¹ on
409 HAP while much higher value, 550 μmol CO₂ g⁻¹, was obtained by Pastor-Pérez et al.
410 [38] on ceria bare support. Likewise, HAP presents very low oxygen storage capacity,
411 2.9 μmol CO₂ g⁻¹, compared to ceria support (180 μmol CO₂ g⁻¹).

412 Irrespective of the Pd catalyst content, addition of palladium to the carrier generally
413 increases both OSC and OSCC values of HAP (Fig. 6). For example, at 400°C, the OSC
414 value obtained on the Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst, 64.2 μmol CO₂ g⁻¹, is about four times
415 higher than that exhibited by unsupported HAP (Fig. 6b). At the same temperature, it is
416 observed that Pd addition improves the OSCC activity by only 1.6 times (Fig. 6a). This
417 indicates that the effect of palladium on the oxygen storage capacity is more
418 pronounced on the surface of HAP. Bedrane et al. [39] observed similar effect in their
419 Pd/CZ catalysts and reported that metal particles can act as activators for the subsequent
420 migration and storage of oxygen onto the support.

421 Fig. 7 compares the OSCC and OSC values, as a function of temperature, per total
422 amount of palladium for the three Pd catalysts. The OSCC of the Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst
423 increases from 0.64 mol_{CO2} mol_{Pd}⁻¹ at 150 °C to 2.34 mol_{CO2} mol_{Pd}⁻¹ at 300 °C and 4.2
424 mol_{CO2} mol_{Pd}⁻¹ at 400 °C (Fig. 7a). These values are significantly higher than those
425 corresponding to Pd(1)/HAP and Pd(2)/HAP catalysts; where the series of the catalysts
426 follows this trend: Pd(0.5)/HAP > Pd(1)/HAP > Pd(2)/HAP. Fig. 7b reports the
427 variation of CO₂ amounts, as a function of temperature, extracted from the OSC study.
428 A comparison of the OSC values of the investigated Pd(x)/HAP catalysts shows that
429 they keep the trend observed in the OSCC study. For instance, at 300 °C, the OSC
430 decreases from 0.94 mol_{CO2} mol_{Pd}⁻¹ for Pd(0.5)/HAP to 0.49 mol_{CO2} mol_{Pd}⁻¹ for
431 Pd(1)/HAP and 0.25 mol_{CO2} mol_{Pd}⁻¹ for Pd(2)/HAP. These data suggest a notable
432 improvement of the reducibility and the oxygen mobility of Pd species exhibiting
433 relatively high dispersion on the HAP support. Similar conclusions were extracted by
434 Reina et al. [40] which reported an improvement of oxygen mobility on supported metal
435 providing higher surface/bulk ratios.

436

437 **3.2. Catalytic activity**

438 **3.2.1. Activity in COTOX reaction**

439 The catalytic activity of the prepared Pd(x)/HAP samples was investigated in the CO
440 oxidation reaction. It should be noted that preliminary experiments (not shown), carried
441 out on the oxidised and reduced Pd(x)/HAP samples, show that the latter exhibit the
442 highest catalytic activity. This is consistent with earlier study from the literature which
443 attributed the high performance of the pre-reduced Pd catalysts to an enhancement of
444 the metal-support interaction, the formation of oxygen vacancies and enrichment in the
445 surface hydroxyl groups [41].

446 Fig. 8a displays the CO conversion as a function of the COTOX reaction temperature
447 over the reduced Pd(x)/HAP catalysts (light-off curves). With the reactor filled up with
448 pure HAP the reaction starts around 150 °C to reach 50% of CO conversion at 280 °C;
449 but it does not exceed 85% at 350 °C. Nevertheless, this behaviour evidences the
450 superiority of HAP activity when compared with alumina bare support [42]. The latter
451 did not reach 15% conversion even for temperatures higher than 350 °C. Addition of
452 palladium to the HAP carrier markedly improves its catalytic behaviour (Fig. 8a).
453 Indeed, over the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts the activity begins around 110°C and the CO
454 conversion increases rapidly to reach 100% at about 225 °C. As reported in Table 4, the
455 Pd loading does not affect significantly the temperature required for 50% (T_{50})
456 CO conversion (204-209°C). The latter are slightly lower than that reported by Gaudet
457 et al. [30] over their Pd/Al₂O₃ system where the corresponding T_{50} value reached 212
458 °C. Likewise, our T_{50} values are much lower than that of Pd/SiO₂ catalyst (275 °C),
459 reported by Liu et al. [43]. A second catalytic run, performed on the same catalysts,
460 shows a reproducibility of the obtained results. Table 4 also shows the turnover
461 frequencies (TOF) values, normalised as the number of reacted CO molecules per
462 surface Pd active sites determined by H₂ chemisorption and the values of the apparent
463 activation energy determined in the temperature range of 125-175 °C. The TOF values
464 calculated at 110 °C, 140 °C and 175 °C seem to decrease significantly with the Pd
465 loading increase. For instance, at 140 °C the TOF decreases from $36.6 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the
466 Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst to $21 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for Pd(2)/HAP. Likewise, at 175 °C, the
467 Pd(0.5)/HAP ($133.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$) results two time more active than the Pd(2)/HAP catalyst
468 ($67.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$). Taking into account the similar active Pd surface area measured on the
469 three catalysts ($0.42\text{-}0.47 \text{ m}^2_{\text{Pd}} \text{ g}^{-1}$) this tendency suggests that the Pd particle size plays
470 a key role in the activity of the investigated Pd(x)/HAP catalysts in COTOX reaction. In

471 agreement with our TEM and H₂ chemisorptions studies highly dispersed Pd species
472 exhibiting the smallest Pd particles size are detected on the Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst. This
473 finding points out that over Pd(x)/HAP catalysts the CO oxidation is a structure-
474 sensitive catalytic reaction. It should be noted that the structure-sensitivity of CO
475 oxidation on the Pd catalysts is a subject of controversy. For instance, in agreement with
476 our activity results, Jin et al. [44] reported that the catalytic activity of their Pd/ZnO
477 catalysts in CO oxidation was significantly enhanced when the size of Pd nanocrystals
478 was reduced from 18 nm to 6 nm. By contrast, in their study on the effect of Pd
479 dispersion on the catalytic activity of Pd/Al₂O₃ systems in CO oxidation, Haneda et al.
480 [14] claimed that the CO oxidation over Pd/Al₂O₃ is a structure-insensitive reaction.
481 A comparison of our results with those reported in previous study [30] shows that lower
482 TOF values were obtained over Pd/Al₂O₃ systems which did not exceed $1.92 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$
483 at 110 °C (versus $5.4\text{-}7.1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ over Pd(x)/HAP catalysts). This comparison proves
484 that the HAP appears as a good alternative to the alumina support. Table 1 also lists the
485 textural properties of the assayed catalysts in the COTOX reaction. The results show
486 that no significant changes are observed in their specific surface areas and in their mean
487 pore size after two reaction cycles. Similar results were reported by Shen et al. [45] in
488 their study on the activity of Pd catalysts supported on phosphorous modified alumina
489 support. They found that the interaction between Pd clusters and P-O-Al units in the P-
490 doped Al₂O₃ prevents the sintering of Pd and the phase segregation of AlPO₄ in γ -
491 Al₂O₃.
492 On the other hand, the apparent activation energies values, obtained from Arrhenius
493 plots, are almost similar (59-60 kJ mol⁻¹) suggesting that irrespective of the used Pd
494 catalyst the CO oxidation reaction occurs through the same mechanism (Table 4). Note

495 that the obtained values are in good agreement with a number of earlier studies dealing
496 with the oxidation of CO over Pd catalysts [30,46].

497 In order to examine the stability of the prepared Pd(x)/HAP samples catalytic runs were
498 conducted at 175 °C for a considerably prolonged reaction time interval (6 h) (Fig. 8b).
499 As expected, the Pd(0.5)/HAP sample exhibits the highest initial conversion value
500 (33%) compared to 15% for Pd(1)/HAP and 9% for Pd(2)/HAP. However, CO
501 conversion over the former rapidly decreases during the first 2 h after which it tends to
502 reach a stationary state corresponding to a conversion of 19%. By contrast, over the
503 Pd(1)/HAP and Pd(2)/HAP catalysts lower rates of deactivation are observed. The
504 difference in the deactivation rate between the catalysts can be attributed to the capacity
505 of each one to strongly adsorb CO. Our CO-TPD study, discussed above, highlights the
506 presence of extra sites, which adsorb strongly the CO molecules, on the Pd(0.5)/HAP
507 catalyst surface. This may explain the high rate of deactivation observed on this catalyst
508 due to the blockage of the active sites by CO.

509 Given the promising behavior of Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst additional experiments were
510 performed to obtain a simple power law that describes the kinetics of the CO oxidation.
511 The reaction rates were determined at 160 °C for low CO conversions, which
512 corresponds to differential reactor conditions, and ensuring stable activity of the
513 catalyst. Fig. S2(a) and Fig. S2(b) (supporting information) show the effect of CO and
514 O₂ partial pressures, respectively, on the CO oxidation reaction rate. The latter seems to
515 increase monotonically with O₂ partial pressure while it decreases with CO partial
516 pressure; so a negative order with respect to CO is expected. Furthermore, logarithmic
517 plot showing the dependence of the reaction rate on the CO and O₂ partial pressures are
518 displayed in Fig. 9a and Fig. 9b, respectively. The analysis of the obtained results shows
519 that the reaction order of CO and O₂ are -0.30 and 0.46, respectively. These kinetic data

520 are consistent with those reported by Satsuma et al. [47] over Pd/Al₂O₃, Pd/ZrO₂ and
521 Pd/SiO₂ catalysts. So, they proposed Langmuir-Hinshelwood mechanism involving a
522 dissociation of oxygen molecule on the metal surface. They attributed, moreover, the
523 negative order respect to CO to self-poisoning of Pd surface by strongly adsorbed CO at
524 low temperatures.

525

526 **3.2.2. Activity in COPROX**

527 Fig. 10a and Fig. 10b show the curves corresponding to the CO conversion and the
528 selectivity to the CO₂ formation, in the COPROX reaction, over the Pd(x)/HAP
529 catalysts. Note that carbon dioxide is the unique carbonaceous product detected (no
530 formation of CH₄ is observed). Table 5 lists the temperatures corresponding to a
531 conversion of 10%, the TOF determined at 175 °C and the activation energy values in
532 the temperature range 100-175 °C.

533 As shown in Fig. 10 two temperature regions could be discussed in the activity profiles:
534 at low temperatures (≤ 275 °C) X_{CO} increases with temperature to achieve 24% at 275
535 °C and a selectivity around 12%. When compared to their activity in the COTOX
536 reaction the activity in the COPROX appears to be strongly influenced by the presence
537 of H₂ in the gas mixture. For instance, at 100 °C, under the COPROX reactants gas
538 mixture, X_{CO} reaches 6% on the Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst while it is negligible in the
539 COTOX reaction. Therefore, the enhanced low temperature reaction activity (75 °C $\leq T$
540 < 150 °C) could be attributed to the presence of H₂ which promotes the initiation of the
541 CO oxidation. This promotional effect of H₂ on CO oxidation was reported in several
542 studies dealing with the activity of noble metals catalysts in the COPROX reaction [48-
543 50].

544 By contrast, at high temperatures both X_{CO} and S_{CO_2} decrease with the reaction
545 temperature suggesting the main occurrence of the H_2 oxidation at the expense of the
546 CO oxidation. These results are in good agreement with earlier studies dealing with the
547 activity of Pd supported catalysts in COPROX [51-52]. They explained the low activity
548 at higher temperature to the presence of hydrogen which is preferentially adsorbed and
549 easily oxidised, rather than CO, on metallic Pd. Moreover, as reported in Table 1, the
550 characterization of Pd(x)/HAP post-reaction catalysts by N_2 physisorption techniques
551 shows an apparent drop in their specific surface areas (about 31-35%). These results
552 were, however, expected in the presence of very high concentration of H_2 (60%) and
553 water vapor as a product of its oxidation [54]. Nevertheless, CO conversion over the
554 Pd(x)/HAP catalysts exceeds significantly that obtained over 1% Pd/CeO₂ catalyst used
555 in the same O₂ excess conditions ($\lambda=2$). The CO conversion on the latter, previously
556 reported by Pozdnyakova et al. [51], did not reach 12% even at 300 °C (versus 17-24%
557 reached over our Pd(x)/HAP catalysts). The performance of our Pd supported catalysts
558 is also compared with that of 1%Pd/Ce_{0.63}Zr_{0.37}O₂ catalysts reported by Mariño et al.
559 [53]. The latter obtained lower values in terms of CO conversions (< 10%) and
560 selectivity (< 15%) in all the investigated temperature range (50-250 °C). This
561 comparison shows a clear catalytic performance superiority of our Pd(x)/HAP catalysts.
562 The TOF values determined at 175 °C are included in Table 5. Over the Pd(0.5)/HAP
563 and Pd(1)/HAP catalysts the TOF are about $110 \times 10^{-3} s^{-1}$ whereas the lowest value ($84 \times$
564 $10^{-3} s^{-1}$) is obtained on the Pd(2)/HAP catalyst. The difference between the Pd(x)/HAP
565 catalysts is probably related to the distribution of the active palladium species. The
566 superior activity of the Pd(0.5)/HAP and Pd(1)/HAP samples suggests that they possess
567 more efficient palladium sites than those deposited on Pd(2)/HAP catalyst. According to
568 the TEM and H_2 chemisorption results on the latter larger Pd particles are deposited

569 which also makes it less active and stable, at 175 °C, during 6 h on stream (Fig. 10c).
570 The activation energy values on the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts are also listed in Table 5.
571 These values, 16.5-26.4 kJ mol⁻¹, are considered very low when compared to those
572 obtained in the COTOX reaction (about 60 kJ mol⁻¹). Hence, this overall activation
573 energy barrier lowering is consistent with the above-mentioned proposal which points
574 out the promotional effect of H₂ on the CO oxidation reaction.

575

576 **3.2.3. Activity in WGS reaction**

577 The performance and the stability of the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts were also studied in the
578 WGS reaction. The catalysts were submitted to the same pre-treatment routine realized
579 before the COTOX and the COPROX experiments (reduction at 200 °C). Fig. 11a and
580 Fig. 11b show the light-off curves and the CO conversion as function of time on stream
581 (at 275 °C), respectively.

582 On all the assayed Pd(x)/HAP samples CO activation starts around 150 °C after which,
583 depending on the Pd loading, the conversion increases with the reaction temperature via
584 different pathways (Fig. 11a). For instance, the Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst exhibits the lowest
585 temperature required to reach a conversion of 10% (300 °C) whereas higher
586 temperatures are needed in the case of Pd(1)/HAP and Pd(2)/HAP catalysts (345 °C and
587 385 °C, respectively). Likewise, the catalyst with the highest palladium loading (2%)
588 exhibits the poorest performance at 400 °C with a conversion lower than 12%. This may
589 be associated to the low dispersion of Pd and, then, the low density of the metal-support
590 interface sites required for the WGS reaction [22]. However, the Pd(0.5)/HAP sample
591 proves the best catalytic performance at 400 °C with a conversion reaching 26%. As
592 discussed above, it is probably the metal-support interaction features that make of the
593 hydroxyapatite such interesting carrier. For instance, in their study on the WGS reaction

594 over Pd/Al₂O₃ catalysts, Lupescu et al. [22] found a conversion below 11% at 400 °C.
595 They attributed the poor activity of their catalysts to the lack of oxygen mobility in the
596 support material. On another hand, the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts demonstrate good
597 resistance against surface area loss (Table 1).

598 Fig. 11b displays the activity of the Pd(x)/HAP as a function of time on stream at 275
599 °C. A comparison of the initial conversion shows that the Pd(0.5)/HAP sample presents
600 the highest value (9%) compared to 5% for Pd(1)/HAP and 6% for Pd(2)/HAP.
601 However, on all the assayed catalysts, CO conversion presents an apparent instability
602 during the first 1 h. After this instability period the activity stays almost constant
603 corresponding to a conversion of 7% for Pd(0.5)/HAP, 4% for Pd(1)/HAP and 3% for
604 Pd(2)/HAP catalyst.

605 Table 5 also lists the specific catalytic activity (TOF, at 275 °C) and the activation
606 energy values for the three Pd(x)/HAP catalysts. A comparison of the apparent E_a for
607 the assayed samples, 44.3-59.7 kJ mol⁻¹, to those reported in the literature shows that
608 they are quite similar [22]. The TOF values seem to follow similar tendency compared
609 to that observed in COTOX and COPROX reactions. Indeed, TOF decreases from 47 ×
610 10⁻³ s⁻¹ over Pd(0.5)/HAP to 22 × 10⁻³ s⁻¹ for Pd(2)/HAP. It is admitted that the activity
611 in WGS reaction is related to the reducibility and the oxygen storage capacity of the
612 catalyst [22]. In this sense, the high performance of our Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst could be
613 explained by the presence of small Pd particle sizes that present higher reducibility and
614 higher oxygen storage capacity.

615

616 **4. Conclusion**

617 Pd(x)/hydroxyapatite catalysts (0.5 ≤ x ≤ 2) have been synthesized and characterized by
618 a wide number of analytical techniques including N₂ physisorption, XRD, H₂-TPR, H₂

619 chemisorption, TEM, CO-TPD, OSCC and OSC techniques. The characterisation
620 results show the presence of a fraction representing 0.3 wt.% Pd which has been
621 incorporated into the hydroxyapatite network and the deposition of Pd species spread as
622 metallic Pd over the carrier. The chemical and physical properties of the latter are
623 affected by the Pd content. Due to its smaller Pd particle sizes the Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst
624 demonstrates stronger CO adsorption, higher reducibility in the presence of CO and
625 higher oxygen mobility compared to the high loading samples (1% and 2%). These
626 interesting features seem to contribute in the enhancement of the activity and selectivity
627 in the three investigated CO elimination processes (COTOX, COPROX and WGS). By
628 contrast, despite exhibiting similar active Pd surface area, compared to those measured
629 on Pd(0.5)/HAP and Pd(1)/HAP, the Pd-rich catalyst (2%) exhibits the poorest
630 performance. This finding points out that over Pd(x)/HAP catalysts the CO oxidation
631 via the three processes is a structure-sensitive catalytic reaction where the distribution of
632 the Pd species plays a key role in their performance. Moreover, the performances of the
633 Pd/HAP catalysts evidence the potential of HAP support as promising alternative to
634 those reported in the available literature.

635 Work is in progress toward improving the activity and selectivity of Pd(x)/HAP
636 catalysts through the use of promoters.

637

638 **5. Acknowledgements**

639 The financial support for this work provided by Gobierno Vasco (GIC IT-657-13) and
640 Ministerio de Economía y Competitividad (ENE2013-41187-R) is gratefully
641 acknowledged. Likewise, the technical support provided by SGIker (UPV/EHU) is
642 gratefully acknowledged.

643

644 **6. References**

- 645 [1] K. Liu, A. Wang, T. Zhang, *ACS Catal.* 2 (2012) 1165-1178.
- 646 [2] Z. Boukha, J.L. Ayastuy, A. Iglesias-González, B. Pereda-Ayo, M.A. Gutiérrez-
647 Ortiz, J.R. González-Velasco, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 40 (2015) 7318-7328.
- 648 [3] Z. Boukha, J.L. Ayastuy, A. Iglesias-González, B. Pereda-Ayo, M.A. Gutiérrez-
649 Ortiz, J.R. González-Velasco, *Appl. Catal. B* 160-161 (2014) 629-640.
- 650 [4] N.K. Gamboa-Rosales, J.L. Ayastuy, Z. Boukha, N. Bion, D. Duprez, J.A. Pérez-
651 Omil, E. del Río, M.A. Gutiérrez-Ortiz, *Appl. Catal. B* 168–169 (2015) 87-97.
- 652 [5] Y. Zhou, Z. Wang, C. Liu, *Catal. Sci. Technol.* 5 (2015) 69-81.
- 653 [6] A. Satsuma, K. Osaki, M. Yanagihara, J. Ohyama, K. Shimizu, *Appl. Catal. B* 132-
654 133 (2013) 511-518
- 655 [7] H. Zhu, Z. Qin, W. Shan, W. Shen, J. Wang, *J. Catal.* 225 (2004) 267-277.
- 656 [8] L. Liu, F. Zhou, L. Wang, X. Qi, F. Shi, Y. Deng, *J. Catal.* 274 (2010) 1-10.
- 657 [9] D.I. Kochubey, S.N. Pavlova, B.N. Novgorodov, G.N. Kryukova, V.A. Sadykov, J.
658 *Catal.* 161 (1996) 500-506.
- 659 [10] Y. Li, Y. Yu, J.-. Wang, J. Song, Q. Li, M. Dong, C.-. Liu, *Appl. Catal. B* 125
660 (2012) 189-196.
- 661 [11] K. Tanikawa, C. Egawa, *Appl. Catal. A* 403 (2011) 12-17.
- 662 [12] R.S. Johnson, A. DeLaRiva, V. Ashbacher, B. Halevi, C.J. Villanueva, G.K. Smith,
663 S. Lin, A.K. Datye, H. Guo, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 15 (2013) 7768-7776.
- 664 [13] Y. Zhou, Z. Wang, C. Liu, *Catal. Sci. Technol.* 5 (2015) 69-81.
- 665 [14] M. Haneda, M. Todo, Y. Nakamura, M. Hattori, *Catal. Today* doi:
666 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2016.05.025>.
- 667 [15] S.H. Oh, R.M. Sinkevitch, *J. Catal.* 142 (1993) 254.

668 [16] O. Pozdnyakova, D. Teschner, A. Wootsch, J. Kröhnert, B. Steinhauer, H. Sauer,
669 L. Toth, F.C. Jentoft, A. Knop-Gericke, Z. Paál, R. Schlögl, *J. Catal.* 237 (2006) 17-28.
670 [17] F. Marino, C. Descorme, D. Duprez, *Appl. Catal. B* 54 (2004) 59-66.
671 [18] Y. Sekine, T. Chihara, R. Watanabe, Y. Sakamoto, M. Matsukata, E. Kikuchi,
672 *Catal. Lett.* 140 (2010) 184-188.
673 [19] Y. Sekine, H. Takamatsu, S. Aramaki, K. Ichishima, M. Takada, M. Matsukata, E.
674 Kikuchi, *Appl. Catal. A* 352 (2009) 214-222.
675 [20] S. Hilaire, X. Wang, T. Luo, R.J. Gorte, J. Wagner, *Appl. Catal. A* 215 (2001) 271-
676 278.
677 [21] T. Bunluesin, R.J. Gorte, G.W. Graham, *Appl. Catal. B* 15 (1998) 107-114.
678 [22] J.A. Lupescu, J.W. Schwank, K.A. Dahlberg, C.Y. Seo, G.B. Fisher, S.L.
679 Peczonczyk, K. Rhodes, M.J. Jagner, L.P. Haack, *Appl. Catal. B* 183 (2016) 343-360.
680 [23] J.A. Lupescu, J.W. Schwank, G.B. Fisher, X. Chen, S.L. Peczonczyk, A.R. Drews,
681 *Appl. Catal. B* 185 (2016) 189-202.
682 [24] Z. Boukha, J. González-Prior, B.d. Rivas, J.R. González-Velasco, R. López-
683 Fonseca, J.I. Gutiérrez-Ortiz, *Appl. Catal. B* 190 (2016) 125-136.
684 [25] Z. Boukha, M. Kacimi, M.F.R. Pereira, J.L. Faria, J.L. Figueiredo, M. Ziyad, *Appl.*
685 *Catal. A* 317 (2007) 299-309.
686 [26] Z. Boukha, M. Kacimi, M. Ziyad, A. Ensuque, F. Bozon-Verduraz, *J. Mol. Catal.*
687 *A* 270 (2007) 205-213.
688 [27] A. Borodzinski, M. Bonarowska, *Langmuir* 13 (1997) 5613-5620.
689 [28] M.A. Aramendia, V. Borau, C. Jimenez, J.M. Marinas, A. Moreno, *Colloid.*
690 *Surface. A* 106 (1996) 161-165
691 [29] J.L. Ayastuy, A. Gurbani, M.P. González-Marcos, M.A. Gutiérrez-Ortiz, *Ind. Eng.*
692 *Chem. Res.* 48 (2009) 5633-5641.

693 [30] J.R. Gaudet, A. de la Riva, E.J. Peterson, T. Bolin, A.K. Datye, *ACS Catal.* 3 (5)
694 (2013) 846-855.

695 [31] J. Panpranot, O. Tangjitwattakorn, P. Praserthdam, J.G. Goodwin, *Appl. Catal. A*
696 292 (2005) 322-327.

697 [32] W.J. Shen, M. Okumura, Y. Matsumura, M. Haruta, *Appl. Catal. A* 213 (2001)
698 225-232.

699 [33] G. Neri, M.G. Musolino, C. Milone, D. Pietropaolo, S. Glavagno, *Appl. Catal. A*
700 208 (2001) 307-316.

701 [34] J. Wang, H. Chen, Z. Hu, M. Yao, Y. Li, *Catal. Rev. Sci. Eng.* 57 (2015) 79-144.

702 [35] F.B. Noronha, M.A.S. Baldanza, M. Schmal, *J. Catal.* 188 (1999) 270-280.

703 [36] J.S. Rieck, A.T. Bell, *J. Catal.* 96 (1985) 88-105.

704 [37] J.S. Rieck, A.T. Bell, *J. Catal.* 103 (1987) 46-54.

705 [38] L. Pastor-Pérez, T.R. Reina, S. Ivanova, M.A. Centeno, J.A. Odriozola, A.
706 Sepúlveda-Escribano, *Catalysts* 5 (2015) 298-309.

707 [39] S. Bedrane, C. Descorme, D. Duprez, *Catal. Today* 73 (2002) 233-238.

708 [40] T.R. Reina, S. Ivanova, J.J. Delgado, I. Ivanov, V. Idakiev, T. Tabakova, M.A.
709 Centeno, J.A. Odriozola, *ChemCatChem* 6 (2014) 1401-1409.

710 [41] M. Jin, J. Park, J.K. Shon, J.H. Kim, Z. Li, Y. Park, J.M. Kim, *Catal. Today* 185
711 (2012) 183-190.

712 [42] T.R. Reina, S. Ivanova, M.A. Centeno, J.A. Odriozola, *Front. Chem.* 12 (2013) 1-9.

713 [43] X. Liu, R. Wang, L. Song, H. He, G. Zhang, X. Zi, W. Qiu, *Catal. Commun.* 46
714 (2014) 213-218.

715 [44] M. Jin, H. Liu, H. Zhang, Z. Xie, J. Liu, Y. Xia, *Nano. Res.* 4 (2011) 83-91.

716 [45] M. Shen, L. Song, J. Wang, X. Wang, *Catal. Commun.* 22 (2012) 28-33.

717 [46] Y. Li, Y. Yu, J. Wang, J. Song, Q. Li, M. Dong, C. Liu, *Appl. Catal. B* 125 (2012)
718 189-196.

719 [47] A. Satsuma, K. Osaki, M. Yanagihara, J. Ohyama, K. Shimizu, *Appl. Catal. B* 132-
720 133 (2013) 511-518.

721 [48] T. Nguyen, F. Morfin, M. Aouine, F. Bosselet, J. Rousset, L. Piccolo, *Catal. Today*
722 253 (2015) 106-114.

723 [49] S. Salomons, R.E. Hayes, M. Votsmeier, *Appl. Catal. A* 352 (2009) 27-34.

724 [50] M.J. Kahlich, H.A. Gasteiger, R.J. Behm, *J. Catal.* 171 (1997) 93-105.

725 [51] O. Pozdnyakova, D. Teschner, A. Wootsch, J. Kröhnert, B. Steinhauer, H. Sauer,
726 L. Toth, F.C. Jentoft, A. Knop-Gericke, Z. Paál, R. Schlögl, *J. Catal.* 237 (2006) 17-28.

727 [52] M. Navlani-García, I. Miguel-García, A. Berenguer-Murcia, D. Lozano-Castelló,
728 D. Cazorla-Amorósa and H. Yamashita, *Catal. Sci. Technol.* 6 (2016) 2623.

729 [53] F. Mariño, C. Descorme, D. Duprez, *Appl. Catal. B* 54 (2004) 59.

730 [54] C.H. Bartholomew, *Appl. Catal. A* 212 (2001) 17-60.

731

732

733

734

735

736

737

738

739

740

741

742 **CAPTIONS FOR TABLES AND FIGURES**

- Table 1 Chemical composition and textural properties of the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts (calcined, reduced and used in COTOX, COPROX and WGR reactions).
- Table 2 XRD and TEM data for the reduced Pd(x)/HAP catalysts.
- Table 3 H₂-TPR, H₂ chemisorptions and CO-TPD data for the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts.
- Table 4 Activity data of Pd(x)/HAP catalysts in the COTOX reaction.
- Table 5 Activity data of Pd(x)/HAP catalysts in the COPROX and WGS reactions.
- Fig. 1 (a) XRD patterns of the reduced Pd(x)/HAP catalysts and (b) their magnification in the 2θ angles range of 30°-37°.
- Fig. 2 TEM micrographs of the reduced Pd(x)/HAP catalysts.
- Fig. 3 H₂-TPR profiles of the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts.
- Fig. 4 Pd particle size, determined by (a) TEM and (b) H₂ chemisorption, dependence on the H₂(II)/Pd molar ratio (determined by H₂-TPR).
- Fig. 5 TPD-MS study of CO pre-adsorbed on Pd(x)/HAP: spectra corresponding to the (a) m/z=28 and (b) m/z=44 signals
- Fig. 6 Evolution of (a) OSCC and (b) OSC as a function of temperature over HAP bare support and Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst.
- Fig. 7 Evolution of (a) OSCC and (b) OSC as a function of temperature over Pd(x)/HAP catalysts.
- Fig. 8 CO oxidation over Pd(x)/HAP catalysts: (a) Light-off curves and (b) CO conversion at 175 °C as a function of time on stream
- Fig. 9 Logarithmic plot of reaction rate at 160 °C vs partial pressure of (a) CO and (b) O₂ over Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst.

Fig. 10 Activity of the Pd(x)HAP catalysts in COPROX: (a) CO conversion, (b) selectivity to CO₂ and (c) CO conversion at 175 °C as a function of time on stream

Fig. 11 WGS reaction over Pd(x)/HAP catalysts: (a) Light-off curves and (b) CO conversion at 275 °C as a function of time on stream

743

Catalysts	Pd, wt. %		$S_{\text{BET}}, \text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$	Pore volume, $\text{cm}^3 \text{g}^{-1}$	Pore size, nm
HAP	0.00 (1.50)	Calcined	52.0	0.45	30.3
		Calcined	48.0	0.39	28.0
Pd(0.5)/HAP	0.56 (1.51)	Reduced	44.0	0.37	31.3
		COTOX	45.0	0.39	28.7
		COPROX	29.0	0.32	28.3
		WGS	46.0	0.39	28.3
Pd(1)/HAP	0.99 (1.52)	Calcined	48.0	0.40	30.0
		Reduced	44.0	0.38	30.8
		COTOX	43.0	0.32	27.8
		COPROX	30.0	0.32	30.4
		WGS	46.0	0.41	29.4
Pd(2)/HAP	2.05 (1.53)	Calcined	48.0	0.37	29.0
		Reduced	42.0	0.35	30.5
		COTOX	44.0	0.35	26.6
		COPROX	27.0	0.30	27.0
		WGS	44.0	0.39	28.6

Values in brackets correspond to (Ca+Pd)/P molar ratios.

Table 1

744
745
746

747

748

749

Catalysts	XRD			TEM		
	(a±0.01), Å	(c±0.002), Å	V, Å ³	D _{TEM} , %	d, nm	S _{Pd} , m ² /g _{cat}
HAP	9.3414	6.8198	515.4	-	-	-
HAP (1.67) ^(*)	9.4154	6.8792	528.1	-	-	-
Pd(0.5)/HAP	9.3713	6.8438	520.5	19.0	7.6	0.45
Pd(1)/HAP	9.3802	6.8418	521.3	10.4	13.1	0.49
Pd(2)/HAP	9.3941	6.8319	522.1	8.4	16.3	0.79

750

^(*) Values extracted from “JCPDS 01-082-2956” reference card.

751

752

Table 2

753

754

755

756

757

758

759

Catalysts	H ₂ -TPR					H ₂ chemisorption			CO-TPD	
	Peak I ^(a) μmol g ⁻¹	Peak II ^(b) μmol g ⁻¹	H ₂ (I)/Pd	H ₂ (II)/Pd	H ₂ ^(R) /Pd ^(c)	D _{chem} , %	d, nm	S _{Pd} , m ² /g _{cat}	CO, μmol g ⁻¹	CO ₂ , μmol g ⁻¹
Pd(0.5)/HAP	23.3	3.4	0.5	0.07	0.43	21.3	5.6	0.46	182	4.0
Pd(1)/HAP	77.0	10.2	0.8	0.11	0.69	9.2	15.3	0.42	215	2.7
Pd(2)/HAP	182.0	29.0	1.0	0.15	0.85	5.0	28.1	0.44	230	2.9

760

761

(a) Total amounts of H₂ consumed at 22 °C.

762

(b) Amounts of released H₂ at 68 °C.

763

(c) Data corresponding to actual amounts of consumed H₂ for the reduction process (H₂^(R)/Pd= H₂(I)/Pd - H₂(II)/Pd).

764

765

766

767

Table 3

768

769

770
771
772
773
774
775
776

Catalysts	T ₅₀ , °C	TOF ₁₁₀ (× 10 ³ s ⁻¹)	TOF ₁₄₀ (× 10 ³ s ⁻¹)	TOF ₁₇₅ (× 10 ³ s ⁻¹)	E _a , kJ mol ⁻¹ (125-175°C)
Pd(0.5)/HAP	204	7.1	36.6	133.8	62.3
Pd(1)/HAP	207	5.4	31.1	113.0	61.9
Pd(2)/HAP	209	6.5	21.0	67.2	59.8

777
778
779
780
781
782
783
784
785
786
787
788
789
790
791
792

Table 4

793
794
795
796

Catalysts	COPROX			WGS		
	T ₁₀ , °C	TOF ₁₇₅ (× 10 ³ s ⁻¹)	E _a , kJ mol ⁻¹ (125-175°C)	T ₁₀ , °C	TOF ₂₇₅ (× 10 ³ s ⁻¹)	E _a , kJ mol ⁻¹ (225-325°C)
Pd(0.5)/HAP	160	110	19.7	300	47.3	56.3
Pd(1)/HAP	177	112	16.5	345	40.0	44.3
Pd(2)/HAP	187	84	26.4	385	21.8	59.7

797
798
799
800
801
802
803
804
805
806
807
808
809
810
811
812
813
814

Table 5

815

816

817

818

819

820

821

822

823

824

825

Figure 1

Figure 2

828

829

830

831

832

833

Figure 3

835

836

837

838

839

Figure 4

840

841

842

Figure 5

843

844

845

846

847

Figure 6

848

849

850

Figure 7

851

852

853

Figure 8

854

855

856

857

Figure 9

858

859

860

861

862

Figure 10

863

864

865

866

867

Figure 11

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

HIGHLIGHTS – BULLET POINTS

Palladium supported on calcium-deficient hydroxyapatite catalysts are synthesised and characterised.

0.3 wt% Pd is incorporated into hydroxyapatite structure and deposited Pd with small particle size is favored at low loading.

Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst exhibits the best catalytic performance in COTOX, COPROX and WGS reactions.

The distribution of Pd species plays a decisive role in the oxygen mobility and the activity.

Supplementary Material

[Click here to download Supplementary Material: REV Supporting information 05-08-2016.docx](#)

25 **Abstract**

26

27 The catalytic performance of synthesised calcium-deficient hydroxyapatite supported Pd
28 catalysts are examined for various CO elimination processes, namely CO total
29 oxidation, CO preferential oxidation and water gas shift reactions. The prepared
30 samples loaded with different amounts of palladium (0.5-2%) are thoroughly
31 characterised by a wide number of analytical techniques including N₂ physisorption,
32 XRD, H₂-TPR, TEM, CO-TPD, H₂ chemisorption, OSCC and OSC techniques. The
33 characterisation results show that, besides an incorporation of 0.3 wt% Pd into
34 hydroxyapatite structure, on the Pd(0.5)/HAP sample, small Pd particle sizes (7.6 nm)
35 are deposited on the HAP support surface presenting relatively high dispersion (19%).
36 The OSCC and OSC studies show that the highly dispersed Pd species lying on the
37 HAP surface present high reducibility and high oxygen mobility.

38 In the three investigated CO elimination processes the Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst proves to
39 be highly active and exhibits higher stability compared to that of the Pd(1)/HAP and
40 Pd(2)/HAP catalysts. The catalytic performance of the series of the catalysts
41 demonstrates their structure-sensitivity in the investigated processes. The latter are
42 remarkably enhanced in the presence of small Pd particle sizes which provide high
43 reducibility and high oxygen storage capacity. Moreover, the performances of the
44 Pd/HAP catalysts evidence the potential of HAP support as promising alternative to
45 those reported in the available literature.

46

47 **Keywords:** Hydroxyapatite, Pd particle size, OSC, OSCC, COPROX, WGS.

48

49

50 **1. Introduction**

51 The use of hydrogen as fuel is a promising alternative to produce clean and efficient
52 energy [1,2]. However, due to its production mainly via the reforming of hydrocarbons
53 its purification is necessary to eliminate the traces of CO in the hydrogen stream;
54 especially, when the posterior use can only tolerate very low concentration of CO (<
55 100 ppm) as in the case of the polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cell (PEMFC)
56 applications. For this purpose, the water gas shift reaction (WGSR) and CO preferential
57 oxidation (COPROX) processes are applied as post-reforming stages for removing most
58 of the CO and producing additional H₂.

59 Generally, catalysts for total CO oxidation (COTOX) consist of transition metal oxides
60 (Cu, Co and Mn) and supported noble metal (Pt, Pd, Au and Ru) catalysts [1-4]. Despite
61 the economical consideration that motivates their use the activity of transition metals is
62 still relatively low compared to the promoted noble metals. Moreover, the former are
63 sensitive to H₂O [5]. Among the noble metal catalysts, Pd-based catalysts have attracted
64 a considerable attention during the past several decades.

65 Usually, the Pd active phases are supported on active (such as CeO₂, MnO_x, TiO₂ and
66 Fe₂O₃) or inert (such as Al₂O₃ graphene and SiO₂) metal oxides presenting relatively
67 high specific surface area [5-14]. Liu et al. [8] studied the role of FeO_x support for
68 oxygen supply, compared to alumina support, during CO oxidation reaction. They
69 found that CO oxidation over Pd/FeO_x occurs on two adjacent active sites (Pd for CO
70 and FeO_x for oxygen) with low activation energy (34 kJ mol⁻¹), compared to that
71 obtained on Pd/Al₂O₃ catalyst (71 kJ mol⁻¹), which accounts for the dramatic difference
72 in activity from Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃ supported Pd. Furthermore, the effect of some
73 additives, such as ceria, cobalt, zinc and alkaline earth metals as promoters to enhance
74 the activity of Pd catalysts, has been extensively studied [11-13]. The main objectives

75 are the stabilization of the Pd species structures and the enhancement of the redox
76 properties of the surface active phases which play an important role in the catalytic
77 properties of these systems in CO oxidation.

78 Nevertheless, Pd catalysts show very low activity and selectivity in the presence of
79 hydrogen (COPROX process) [15-17]. The oxidation of H₂ appeared to be greatly
80 favoured at the expense of CO oxidation. Oh et al. [15] associated this low COPROX
81 activity, over their Pd/Al₂O₃ catalysts, with the formation of PdO_x species which are
82 very active in hydrogen oxidation. Also, Pozdnyakova et al. [16] observed a poor
83 activity on Pd catalysts, even with reducible support (CeO₂). They claimed that, in the
84 presence of hydrogen, formation of Pd β-hydride greatly suppressed the possibility of
85 CO oxidation, because oxygen from both gas-phase and support sites (and also from
86 PdO_x) reacts rapidly with H₂ to form water, which desorbs easily.

87 On the other hand, Pd catalysts supported on various supports were also studied in WGS
88 reaction [18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23]. In this case, reducible supports (CeO₂, TiO₂, Fe₂O₃ and
89 Co₂O₃) are frequently used. According to Sekine et al. [19] despite their lower initial
90 activity the Pd/LaCoO₃ catalysts exhibit superior stability compared to Pt/LaCoO₃
91 catalysts. They also reported that Pd-Pt/LaCoO₃ catalyst presents higher activity and
92 stability than that of a commercially available catalyst (Cu-ZnO). Hilaire et al. [20]
93 showed that Pd/ceria exhibited much higher activities than either ceria alone or
94 Pd/silica, demonstrating a cooperative effect between Pd and ceria. Moreover, they
95 proposed a mechanism involving a redox process which consists on the oxidation of
96 reduced ceria by water and then transferring oxygen to the active metal to react with
97 adsorbed CO. In their study on the Pd model catalysts, Pd/Al₂O₃ and Pd/CZ, Lupescu et
98 al. [23] concluded that to prolong the performance throughout the life of the catalyst a

99 relatively high dispersion of Pd should be maintained. This also implies the importance
100 of the support applied to disperse the Pd species.

101 To resume, the applicability of Pd catalyst is a topic of high interest both scientifically
102 and technically. Various supports are used to disperse the Pd species and to generate
103 new interactions which promote their activity. In the present work, we study the
104 applicability of hydroxyapatite (HAP), $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$, as a porous support of the Pd
105 species for three CO elimination processes (COTOX, COPROX and WGS). Our interest
106 in this kind of materials is justified by the flexibility of its crystal structure and its high
107 ion-exchange ability which may lead to the speciation of the metal active phases [24-
108 26]. Moreover, HAP offers the possibility of tuning the surface chemical properties by
109 varying the calcium/phosphorus ratio [24-26]. These interesting characteristics confer to
110 HAP materials a large room for improvement in their catalytic activity and selectivity.
111 Though a number of studies dealing with hydroxyapatite as support are presently
112 available [24-26], to the best of our knowledge, the applications of the prepared
113 Pd(x)/hydroxyapatite in such reactions and our approach to explain their catalytic
114 behavior have not been yet investigated. Interesting conclusions have been drawn from
115 the correlation between the distribution of Pd active species and their performance in
116 the three investigated processes.

117

118 **2. Experimental**

119 **2.1. Preparation of the catalysts**

120 Calcium-deficient hydroxyapatite support (HAP), with Ca/P molar ratio equal to 1.50,
121 was synthesized adding drop wise a boiled aqueous solution of calcium nitrate to a
122 solution of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$. The precipitate was re-dissolved in a nitric acid solution and
123 neutralized with ammonia at pH 10. The resulting mixture was maintained under

124 stirring at 80 °C for 16 h. After filtration, the recovered solid was washed well with
125 purified water then dried at 120 °C and finally calcined at 500 °C for 4 h.

126 The Pd(x)/HAP catalysts were prepared by impregnation of the corresponding support
127 by tetraamminepalladium (II) chloride monohydrate where x is the Pd wt.% content
128 (Table 1). The prepared catalysts were calcined at 500°C (4 h). The activated samples
129 were obtained after a reduction under 20% H₂/He at 200 °C for 2 h followed by a
130 treatment at 500 °C in a flow of pure He.

131

132 **2.2. Characterisation techniques**

133 The volumetric N₂ adsorption at -196 °C was performed on an automatic apparatus
134 Micromeritics, model TRISTAR II 3020 apparatus. The pre-treatments applied to the
135 samples consisted of a cleaning, at 300 °C (overnight), under nitrogen flow. The
136 specific areas of the samples were determined in line with the standard BET procedure,
137 using nitrogen adsorption taken in the relative equilibrium pressure interval of 0.03-0.3.

138 X-ray diffraction (XRD) studies were conducted on a X'PERT-MPD X-ray
139 diffractometer with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) and Ni filter. The X-ray tube was
140 operated at 40 kV and 40 mA. The samples were scanned between 10° and 100° (2θ),
141 and the X-ray diffraction line positions were determined with a step size of 0.01° and a
142 counting time of 2.5 s per step. Phase identification was conducted by comparison with
143 JCPDS database cards.

144 The morphology, size and dispersion of the palladium particles lying on the reduced
145 Pd(x)/HAP surface were examined by transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The
146 TEM studies were performed on a Philips CM200 transmission electron microscope
147 equipped with LaB₆ filament operating at 200 kV and combined with X-ray energy
148 dispersive spectroscopy (X-EDS) techniques. The latter was used to confirm the

149 absence of chlorine phases from our samples surface. The average diameter of
150 palladium particles was obtained from the measurement of at least 300 particles using
151 ImageJ software. The corresponding values for palladium dispersion, D_{TEM} , and specific
152 palladium surface area were calculated according to a procedure previously described
153 by Borodzinski et al. [27].

154 The reducibility of the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts was examined by temperature-programmed
155 reduction (H_2 -TPR) on a Micromeritics AutoChem 2920 instrument equipped with a
156 thermal conductivity detector (TCD). Firstly, all the samples were pre-treated in an
157 oxygen stream ($5\% \text{O}_2/\text{He}$, $50 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$) at $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h and then cooled to $-30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in a
158 flow of He ($50 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$). The reducing gas was $5\% \text{H}_2/\text{Ar}$ with a flow rate of
159 $50 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$. The temperature range explored was from $-30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, with a
160 heating rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$. This temperature was maintained for 30 min. The produced
161 water was trapped in a cold trap, and the consumption of H_2 was quantitatively
162 measured by time integration of the H_2 -TPR profiles.

163 The H_2 chemisorption measurements were carried out on the same experimental setup,
164 used for H_2 -TPR experiments. The catalysts (80 mg) were submitted to a pre-reduction
165 at $200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (2 h) in a flow $5\% \text{H}_2/\text{Ar}$ ($50 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$) followed by a treatment with Ar (50
166 $\text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$) at 500°C . H_2 pulses ($5\% \text{H}_2/\text{Ar}$, loop volume: 0.5 cm^3) were then injected in
167 Ar carrier ($50 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$) over the sample, at $70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [28]. The Pd dispersion, D_{chem} ,
168 defined as the active metal fraction exposed ($D_{\text{chem}} = \text{Pd}_s / \text{Pd}_{\text{tot}}$) was determined on the
169 assumption of a unity adsorption stoichiometry ($\text{H}/\text{Pd}_s = 1$); where “ Pd_s ” represents the
170 surface Pd atoms and “ Pd_{tot} ” represents the total amounts of Pd. The mean diameter of
171 Pd particles was calculated, assuming that Pd particles have a spherical shape, from the
172 following expressions [27]:

173

174 i) For D_{chem} in the range 0.01-0.2: $d(\text{nm}) = 1.404/D_{\text{chem}}$ (1)

175 ii) For D_{chem} in the range 0.2-0.84: $d(\text{nm}) = 1.180/D_{\text{chem}}$ (2)

176 The temperature programmed desorption of CO studies (CO-TPD) were carried out on
177 the same experimental setup, used for H₂-TPR experiments, coupled to a MKS Cirrus
178 LM99 mass spectrometer. The catalysts were submitted to a pre-treatment consisting on
179 their reduction at 200 °C (2 h) in a flow 5%H₂/Ar (50 cm³ min⁻¹) followed by a
180 treatment with He (50 cm³ min⁻¹) at 500°C. The adsorption of CO was performed at -
181 120 °C in a flow of 5%CO/He (50 cm³ min⁻¹) for 1 h. After CO adsorption the samples
182 were treated with He for 1 h and heated at 10 °C min⁻¹ up to 500 °C in flowing He (50
183 cm³ min⁻¹). The MS signals (m/z = 28, 44 and 18) assigned to CO, CO₂ and H₂O,
184 respectively, were followed. Note that the quantification of CO amount was corrected
185 taking into account the contribution of the signal m/z:44.

186 The Oxygen Storage Complete Capacity (OSCC) and Oxygen Storage Capacity (OSC)
187 experiments at different temperatures (150°C, 200°C, 250°C, 300°C, 350°C and 400
188 °C) were carried out on the same experimental setup coupled to MKS Cirrus LM99
189 mass spectrometer. The catalysts (25 mg, 40-80 μm) were submitted to a reduction at
190 200 °C (2 h) in a flow 5%H₂/Ar followed by a treatment with He at 500°C. For the
191 OSCC measurements, the samples were submitted to ten O₂ pulses (5%O₂/He, loop
192 volume: 5 cm³), injected in He carrier, followed by ten CO pulses (5%CO/He, loop
193 volume: 5 cm³). The OSCC values were determined from the sum of the CO₂ amounts
194 formed after each CO pulse. After degas in a He flow OSC measurements were
195 performed on the same samples. The latter were submitted to six alternating series of
196 pulses (CO-O₂) where the OSC was determined as the average amount of the formed
197 CO₂ for each CO pulse.

198

199 2.3. Catalytic tests

200 The catalytic tests were performed, with flow/mass ratio of $1333 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1} \text{ g}^{-1}$, in a
201 tubular flow reactor operating at atmospheric pressure using 150 mg of the catalyst.
202 Prior to running the catalytic experiments, the catalysts were submitted to a pre-
203 treatment routine consisting on their reduction at $200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (2 h) in a flow $20\% \text{ H}_2/\text{He}$
204 followed by a treatment with He at 400°C . Three different feed gas mixtures with the
205 same oxygen excess ($\lambda = 2$ ($P_{\text{O}_2}/P_{\text{CO}} = 2$)) and balanced with He, to reach a total flow
206 rate of $200 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$, were used in each reaction as follows:

- 207 • 1% CO and 1% O₂ in COTOX reaction.
- 208 • 1% CO, 1% O₂ and 60% H₂ in COPROX reaction.
- 209 • 1% CO and 2% H₂O in WGS reaction.

210 The reaction products were continuously analysed by Gas Chromatograph (Agilent
211 Technologies 490 Micro GC) equipped with a TCD detector. Carbon monoxide
212 conversions (X_{CO}) and selectivity to CO₂ (S_{CO_2}) were calculated by using the inlet (F^{in})
213 and outlet (F^{out}) molar flow values of the two reactants (eqn. (3) and eqn. (4),
214 respectively):

$$X_{\text{CO}} (\%) = 100 \cdot \frac{F_{\text{CO}}^{\text{in}} - F_{\text{CO}}^{\text{out}}}{F_{\text{CO}}^{\text{in}}} \quad (3)$$

$$S_{\text{CO}_2} (\%) = 100 \cdot 0.5 \cdot \frac{F_{\text{CO}}^{\text{in}} - F_{\text{CO}}^{\text{out}}}{F_{\text{O}_2}^{\text{in}} - F_{\text{O}_2}^{\text{out}}} \quad (4)$$

215 Turnover frequency (TOF) values were calculated as the activity data per mole of active
216 surface palladium determined by H₂ chemisorption experiments [2-3]. In order to assure
217 differential reactor conditions the temperatures used for the calculations of turnover
218 frequency (TOF) for the three tested reactions over the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts
219 corresponded to low CO conversions (< 20%). The absence of heat and mass transfer
220 limitations were checked following the criterions described elsewhere [29].

221

222 **3. Results and discussion**

223 **3.1. Characterization of the samples**

224 **3.1.1. N₂-physorption (BET measurements)**

225 The textural properties of the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts were examined by nitrogen
226 adsorption-desorption measurements. The experimental N₂ physisorption isotherms for
227 the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts in their calcined and reduced forms (not shown) show that they
228 are characteristic of mesoporous materials exhibiting IV-type according to the IUPAC
229 classification. The specific surface area, pore volume and average pore size are shown
230 in Table1. **Fig. 1S (Supporting information)** shows the pore size distributions for all the
231 reduced catalysts. The pore size distribution corresponding to HAP support and the
232 Pd(x)/HAP catalysts show a broad unimodal distribution centred at approximately
233 32 nm **(Fig. 1S)**. This distribution does not change with the introduction of palladium.
234 However, the addition of palladium (0.5-2%) to HAP produces a slight drop in its
235 specific surface area (up to 19%) and pore volume. For instance, the specific surface
236 area of the resultant catalysts significantly decreases from 52 m² g⁻¹ for the HAP bare
237 support to 48 m² g⁻¹ for the oxidised and 42-44 m² g⁻¹ for the reduced Pd(x)/HAP
238 catalysts. Table 1 also lists the textural data of the used catalysts in the COTOX,
239 COPROX and WGS reactions which will be commented below.

240

241 **3.1.2. X-ray diffraction (XRD)**

242 The Pd(x)/HAP samples were also characterised by means of X-ray powder diffraction
243 in order to investigate the effect of the Pd addition on their structural properties. **Fig. 1a**
244 displays the XR-diffractograms corresponding to the reduced Pd(x)/HAP and HAP bare
245 support samples. The patterns of the latter are characterised by the presence of the

246 maxima at $2\theta = 26.15^\circ, 32.06^\circ, 32.49^\circ, 33.19^\circ$ and 34.32° , among others. As expected,
247 these 2θ angles values are slightly higher than those corresponding to stoichiometric
248 hydroxyapatite used as reference (JCPDS 01-082-2956). This is because of the
249 synthesised support consists of a calcium-deficient hydroxyapatite with Ca/P molar
250 ratio equal to 1.50 (Table 1); lower than the 1.67 expected for a stoichiometric
251 hydroxyapatite ($\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$). In our previous study we explained this non-
252 stoichiometry by a loss of Ca^{2+} ions, which is corrected by insertion of H^+ ions at the
253 expense of hydroxyl groups to ensure electroneutrality [24]. Hence, the general formula
254 of these calcium deficient hydroxyapatite can be denoted as
255 $\text{Ca}_{10-z}(\text{HPO}_4)_z(\text{PO}_4)_{6-z}(\text{OH})_{2-z}$ where $0 < z \leq 1$.

256 On the other hand, it is difficult to evidence the presence of the Pd structure peaks on
257 the diffractograms of Pd(x)/HAP catalysts; especially, the diffraction peaks
258 corresponding to (111), (200), (220) and (311) planes which characterise the presence of
259 metallic palladium structure. This is may be due to the overlapping of the Pd peaks with
260 those of hydroxyapatite structure. Indeed, a comparison between the Pd(x)/HAP
261 samples shows that the peak at 40° is broader on the Pd(1)/HAP and Pd(2)/HAP
262 diffractograms compared to that of Pd(0.5)/HAP and HAP support, suggesting an
263 apparent overlapping of the peak corresponding to metallic Pd (111) with that
264 associated to hydroxyapatite (130).

265 Interestingly, the XRD patterns of the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts show a significant evolution
266 of the hydroxyapatite diffraction peaks which shift to lower angles with Pd loading
267 increasing. For instance, 2θ angle corresponding to (211) reticular plane shifts from
268 32.06° for the HAP sample to 31.93° and 31.89° for Pd(1)/HAP and Pd(2)/HAP
269 samples, respectively (Fig. 1b). These observations suggest that the presence of
270 palladium induces a modification of the cell parameters of the HAP structure. Table 2

271 lists the most important structure parameters in terms of the lattice parameters, “a” and
272 “c”, and unit cell volume (V). Values corresponding to stoichiometric HAP (Ca/P:1.67)
273 are also included for comparison. The reported data show that the lattice parameter “a”
274 increases with increasing the Pd content. Likewise, the lattice parameter “c” calculated
275 in all the Pd catalysts is higher than that of the HAP bare support. This increase in “a”
276 and “c” values with palladium addition induces an apparent increase in the unit cell
277 volume suggesting a progressive incorporation of Pd in the HAP crystal lattice. As the
278 ionic radius of the Pd²⁺ (100 pm) is smaller than that of Ca²⁺ (114 pm) the observed
279 expansion might be due to an incorporation of Pd²⁺ into the cationic vacant sites rather
280 than an ion-exchange process with Ca²⁺ sites.

281

282 **3.1.3. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)**

283 Hydroxyapatite-supported palladium samples, reduced at 200 °C, are investigated by
284 TEM techniques. Fig. 2 shows their corresponding TEM micrographs and particle size
285 distribution diagrams. Examination of the Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst reveals the presence of
286 quasi-spherical Pd particles which are homogeneously dispersed on the support surface.
287 Furthermore, the size distribution trace of these Pd particles consists of a narrow
288 unimodal distribution with an average size of 7.6 nm corresponding to dispersion value
289 of 19% (Table 2). This Pd dispersion value (19%) is consistent with those found by
290 Guadet et al. [30] in their Pd/Al₂O₃ and Pd/La-Al₂O₃ systems (17-25%) presenting
291 similar surface density of the Pd (1.2-1.6 μmol m⁻²). At high Pd loading the particle
292 sizes consist of a broader distribution with an average size of 13.1 nm for Pd(1)/HAP
293 and 16.3 nm for Pd(2)/HAP, with relatively lower dispersion (10.4% and 8.4%,
294 respectively) compared to the catalyst with the lowest Pd loading (Pd(0.5)/HAP).

295 On the other hand, the X-EDS analyses of the Pd(x)/HAP samples after their calcination at 500
296 °C followed by reduction at 200 °C confirm the absence of Cl species on the Pd(x)/HAP surface.

297

298 **3.1.4. H₂-TPR and H₂ chemisorption studies**

299 The H₂-TPR experiments were performed in order to determine the different Pd
300 reducible species present in the prepared Pd(x)/HAP catalysts (Fig. 3). The H₂-TPR
301 profiles included in Fig. 3 show typical spectra for oxidized Pd species consisting of a
302 reduction peak at 22 °C associated with the reduction of Pd oxides (Peak I) and a second
303 negative peak at 68 °C corresponding to palladium hydride (Pd-H) decomposition
304 leading to hydrogen release (Peak II). Generally, the latter could be formed at lower
305 temperatures equivalent to those corresponding to oxidized Pd species reduction [31-
306 33]. Table 3 reports quantitative data corresponding to the integration of the two
307 resulting peaks and the corresponding H₂(I)/Pd and H₂(II)/Pd molar ratios determined as
308 mole of consumed and released H₂ per mole of total palladium, respectively. Moreover,
309 taking into account the formation of Pd hydride concurrently with the reduction of
310 oxidized species of Pd the actual amounts of consumed H₂ for the reduction process
311 (H₂^(R)/Pd) is determined as the difference between the amounts of the consumed and the
312 released H₂ (H₂^(R)/Pd = H₂(I)/Pd - H₂(II)/Pd). For the Pd(0.5)/HAP sample, the
313 calculated H₂^(R)/Pd molar ratio is around 0.43 which is lower than that expected for the
314 reduction of stoichiometric palladium oxide (PdO). This result suggests a presence of a
315 fraction of Pd species which does not reduce in the TPR operating conditions (heating
316 in H₂/Ar at temperatures up to 600 °C). Similar conclusions can be extracted for the
317 Pd(1)/HAP and Pd(2)/HAP samples which also present low H₂^(R)/Pd ratios (0.69 and
318 0.85, respectively). Interestingly, for all the Pd(x)/HAP samples, an estimation of this
319 Pd non-reducible fraction show that it is around 0.29-0.31 wt% of the total weight of the
320 sample. This is a remarkable observation indicating that it represents an upper limit for

321 a certain interaction of Pd species with the HAP support which makes them non-
322 reducible (up to 600 °C). In agreement with the XRD results, which proposed a possible
323 incorporation of Pd into the hydroxyapatite network, we can conclude that the level of
324 such incorporation is limited to 0.3 wt% Pd.

325 Table 3 also lists the Pd dispersion, active Pd surface area and average particle size for
326 the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts as determined from the H₂ chemisorption measurements.
327 Interestingly, the three catalysts exhibit comparable active Pd surface area which is
328 around 0.42-0.47 m_{Pd}² g⁻¹ (Table 3). The comparison of the obtained results with those
329 obtained by TEM techniques shows slight differences in the case of the Pd(0.5)/HAP and
330 Pd(1)/HAP catalysts. By contrast, on the Pd(2)/HAP catalyst the Pd dispersion value
331 measured by H₂ chemisorption results significantly lower (5%) compared to that
332 determined by TEM techniques (8.4%). These observations suggested that, on the Pd-
333 rich catalyst a large fraction of Pd is not accessible to the gas phase.

334 On the other hand, in agreement with a number of earlier studies from the literature the
335 formation of palladium hydride depends on the palladium particle sizes [31-34]. In this
336 sense, it was reported that large Pd particles easily form Pd hydride whereas small Pd
337 particles partially inhibit its formation. According to the determined amounts of
338 released H₂ reported in Table 3 it can be concluded that small Pd particles are deposited
339 on the Pd(0.5)/HAP sample compared to those deposited on the higher Pd loadings
340 samples (1% and 2%). On the latter, the H₂(II)/Pd ratio corresponding to the integration
341 of the negative peak at 68 °C reach relatively higher values (0.11-0.15) which indicate
342 an initiation of the tridimensional growth of Pd particles. In this sense, Fig. 4 shows a
343 clear correlation between the amounts of released H₂ during the H₂-TPR experiments (at
344 68 °C) and the Pd particle sizes determined by TEM (Fig. 4a) and/or those determined
345 by H₂ chemisorptions (Fig. 4b).

346 3.1.5. CO-TPD study

347 The thermal stability of pre-adsorbed CO on the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts was investigated
348 by means of CO-TPD techniques. The TPD profiles of pre-adsorbed CO at -120 °C on
349 the reduced Pd(x)/HAP catalysts are presented in Fig. 5. Data corresponding to the HAP
350 bare support are also included for comparison. Generally, at low temperatures (< 100 °C)
351 the CO desorption peaks are associated with linearly bonded CO (weakly adsorbed CO
352 species) while the desorption peaks centred at high temperatures (> 200 °C) are
353 attributed to bridge-bonded CO (strongly adsorbed CO species) [35].

354 For all the analysed samples large amounts of CO are desorbed at low temperatures
355 which are related to linearly bonded CO (Fig. 5a). As reported in Table 3 the amount of
356 desorbed CO from the HAP, 397 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$, is much higher than those determined for the
357 three Pd catalysts (182-230 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$). It can also be observed that the amount of the
358 weakly adsorbed CO increases with the Pd loadings increase, 182 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ for
359 Pd(0.5)/HAP, 215 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ for Pd(1)/HAP and 230 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ for Pd(2)/HAP. This trend
360 suggests that the high dispersion of Pd tends to decrease the density of the weak-
361 strength adsorption sites of CO. However, the Pd(0.5)/HAP sample exclusively exhibits
362 additional CO desorption peak which occurs at temperature around 290 °C (Fig 5a).
363 This fraction, that represents 4% of the total amount of desorbed CO, can be associated
364 to the highly dispersed Pd species.

365 Fig. 5b displays the profiles of the formation/release of CO₂ during the CO-TPD
366 experiments. It should be noted that in addition to CO₂ formation small amount of H₂O
367 is observed in the desorbing gas (not shown), suggesting the occurrence of the water gas
368 shift reaction of the adsorbed CO with the surface hydroxyl groups of the support [35-
369 37]. On the HAP bare support the release of CO₂ starts around 180 °C which forms a
370 broad desorption peak presenting a maximum at 350 °C (Fig. 5b). By contrast, on the

371 Pd(x)/HAP catalysts the formation of CO₂ starts at relatively lower temperatures
372 (around 100 °C). Likewise, the position of the CO₂ peaks seems to shift toward low
373 temperatures compared with that of HAP. For instance, the Pd(1)/HAP and Pd(2)/HAP
374 samples exhibit a CO₂ production peak at 300 °C while the Pd(0.5)/HAP sample
375 exhibits two peaks at 200 °C and 300 °C. Table 3 also lists the total amounts of desorbed
376 CO₂ extracted from the integration of its corresponding peaks. It can be observed that
377 the addition of palladium onto the HAP surface dramatically increases the amount of the
378 desorbed CO₂. For instance, the surface density of CO₂ desorbed from the support,
379 0.8 μmol g_{cat}⁻¹, is much smaller than that determined for Pd(0.5)/HAP, 4 μmol g_{cat}⁻¹.
380 The latter also demonstrates that it bears more active sites associated with the
381 formation of CO₂ than the Pd(1)/HAP and Pd(2)/HAP catalysts (2.7-2.9 μmol g⁻¹). As
382 suggested by the TPD traces for the three Pd catalysts (Fig. 5b) the loss observed in the
383 density of these active sites observed upon increasing the palladium concentration may
384 be correlated with the disappearance of the CO₂ desorption peak at 200 °C, which can
385 be associated with the presence of highly dispersed Pd species.

386 These remarkable differences between the Pd(x)/HAP samples point out the effect of
387 the Pd dispersion on the amount, distribution and activity of the CO adsorption sites. In
388 this sense, the high dispersion of the Pd species decreases the density of the weak-
389 strength adsorption sites of CO and increases the density of strong adsorption sites by
390 providing extra active sites.

391

392 3.1.6. OSCC and OSC studies

393 The OSCC and OSC studies on the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts in the temperature range
394 between 150 °C and 400°C are summarized in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7. By means of OSCC
395 valuable information about the maximum reducibility of the catalysts can be gained

396 while the OSC results provide a quantification of the most reactive and available
397 oxygen atoms.

398 As reported in Fig. 6a and Fig. 6b negligible amounts of CO₂ are released before
399 200 °C on the HAP bare support. At higher temperatures, oxygen storage sites on the
400 surface may be accessed. As temperature increases, the OSC and OSCC increases
401 proceed via different pathways. OSC does not exceed 17 μmol_{CO₂} g⁻¹ at 400 °C, Fig. 6b,
402 probably because it is limited by the most reactive species located at the support
403 surface. By contrast, much higher OSCC values are obtained in all the range of
404 investigated temperatures (Fig. 6b). For instance it reaches 123 μmol_{CO₂} g⁻¹ at 400 °C.
405 This behavior, which represents the maximum reducibility, suggests that OSCC seems
406 to be controlled by a participation of bulk oxygen. Nevertheless, all the OSCC and OSC
407 values obtained on the HAP bare support, evidence its low activity compared to
408 reducible supports. For instance, at 250 °C the OSCC is around 15 μmol CO₂ g⁻¹ on
409 HAP while much higher value, 550 μmol CO₂ g⁻¹, was obtained by Pastor-Pérez et al.
410 [38] on ceria bare support. Likewise, HAP presents very low oxygen storage capacity,
411 2.9 μmol CO₂ g⁻¹, compared to ceria support (180 μmol CO₂ g⁻¹).

412 Irrespective of the Pd catalyst content, addition of palladium to the carrier generally
413 increases both OSC and OSCC values of HAP (Fig. 6). For example, at 400°C, the OSC
414 value obtained on the Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst, 64.2 μmol CO₂ g⁻¹, is about four times
415 higher than that exhibited by unsupported HAP (Fig. 6b). At the same temperature, it is
416 observed that Pd addition improves the OSCC activity by only 1.6 times (Fig. 6a). This
417 indicates that the effect of palladium on the oxygen storage capacity is more
418 pronounced on the surface of HAP. Bedrane et al. [39] observed similar effect in their
419 Pd/CZ catalysts and reported that metal particles can act as activators for the subsequent
420 migration and storage of oxygen onto the support.

421 Fig. 7 compares the OSCC and OSC values, as a function of temperature, per total
422 amount of palladium for the three Pd catalysts. The OSCC of the Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst
423 increases from $0.64 \text{ mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{ mol}_{\text{Pd}}^{-1}$ at $150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $2.34 \text{ mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{ mol}_{\text{Pd}}^{-1}$ at $300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and 4.2
424 $\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{ mol}_{\text{Pd}}^{-1}$ at $400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Fig. 7a). These values are significantly higher than those
425 corresponding to Pd(1)/HAP and Pd(2)/HAP catalysts; where the series of the catalysts
426 follows this trend: Pd(0.5)/HAP > Pd(1)/HAP > Pd(2)/HAP. Fig. 7b reports the
427 variation of CO_2 amounts, as a function of temperature, extracted from the OSC study.
428 A comparison of the OSC values of the investigated Pd(x)/HAP catalysts shows that
429 they keep the trend observed in the OSCC study. For instance, at $300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the OSC
430 decreases from $0.94 \text{ mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{ mol}_{\text{Pd}}^{-1}$ for Pd(0.5)/HAP to $0.49 \text{ mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{ mol}_{\text{Pd}}^{-1}$ for
431 Pd(1)/HAP and $0.25 \text{ mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{ mol}_{\text{Pd}}^{-1}$ for Pd(2)/HAP. These data suggest a notable
432 improvement of the reducibility and the oxygen mobility of Pd species exhibiting
433 relatively high dispersion on the HAP support. Similar conclusions were extracted by
434 Reina et al. [40] which reported an improvement of oxygen mobility on supported metal
435 providing higher surface/bulk ratios.

436

437 **3.2. Catalytic activity**

438 **3.2.1. Activity in COTOX reaction**

439 The catalytic activity of the prepared Pd(x)/HAP samples was investigated in the CO
440 oxidation reaction. It should be noted that preliminary experiments (not shown), carried
441 out on the oxidised and reduced Pd(x)/HAP samples, show that the latter exhibit the
442 highest catalytic activity. This is consistent with earlier study from the literature which
443 attributed the high performance of the pre-reduced Pd catalysts to an enhancement of
444 the metal-support interaction, the formation of oxygen vacancies and enrichment in the
445 surface hydroxyl groups [41].

446 Fig. 8a displays the CO conversion as a function of the COTOX reaction temperature
447 over the reduced Pd(x)/HAP catalysts (light-off curves). With the reactor filled up with
448 pure HAP the reaction starts around 150 °C to reach 50% of CO conversion at 280 °C;
449 but it does not exceed 85% at 350 °C. Nevertheless, this behaviour evidences the
450 superiority of HAP activity when compared with alumina bare support [42]. The latter
451 did not reach 15% conversion even for temperatures higher than 350 °C. Addition of
452 palladium to the HAP carrier markedly improves its catalytic behaviour (Fig. 8a).
453 Indeed, over the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts the activity begins around 110°C and the CO
454 conversion increases rapidly to reach 100% at about 225 °C. As reported in Table 4, the
455 Pd loading does not affect significantly the temperature required for 50% (T_{50})
456 CO conversion (204-209°C). The latter are slightly lower than that reported by Gaudet
457 et al. [30] over their Pd/Al₂O₃ system where the corresponding T_{50} value reached 212
458 °C. Likewise, our T_{50} values are much lower than that of Pd/SiO₂ catalyst (275 °C),
459 reported by Liu et al. [43]. A second catalytic run, performed on the same catalysts,
460 shows a reproducibility of the obtained results. Table 4 also shows the turnover
461 frequencies (TOF) values, normalised as the number of reacted CO molecules per
462 surface Pd active sites determined by H₂ chemisorption and the values of the apparent
463 activation energy determined in the temperature range of 125-175 °C. The TOF values
464 calculated at 110 °C, 140 °C and 175 °C seem to decrease significantly with the Pd
465 loading increase. For instance, at 140 °C the TOF decreases from $36.6 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the
466 Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst to $21 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for Pd(2)/HAP. Likewise, at 175 °C, the
467 Pd(0.5)/HAP ($133.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$) results two time more active than the Pd(2)/HAP catalyst
468 ($67.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$). Taking into account the similar active Pd surface area measured on the
469 three catalysts ($0.42\text{-}0.47 \text{ m}^2_{\text{Pd}} \text{ g}^{-1}$) this tendency suggests that the Pd particle size plays
470 a key role in the activity of the investigated Pd(x)/HAP catalysts in COTOX reaction. In

471 agreement with our TEM and H₂ chemisorptions studies highly dispersed Pd species
472 exhibiting the smallest Pd particles size are detected on the Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst. This
473 finding points out that over Pd(x)/HAP catalysts the CO oxidation is a structure-
474 sensitive catalytic reaction. It should be noted that the structure-sensitivity of CO
475 oxidation on the Pd catalysts is a subject of controversy. For instance, in agreement with
476 our activity results, Jin et al. [44] reported that the catalytic activity of their Pd/ZnO
477 catalysts in CO oxidation was significantly enhanced when the size of Pd nanocrystals
478 was reduced from 18 nm to 6 nm. By contrast, in their study on the effect of Pd
479 dispersion on the catalytic activity of Pd/Al₂O₃ systems in CO oxidation, Haneda et al.
480 [14] claimed that the CO oxidation over Pd/Al₂O₃ is a structure-insensitive reaction.
481 A comparison of our results with those reported in previous study [30] shows that lower
482 TOF values were obtained over Pd/Al₂O₃ systems which did not exceed $1.92 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$
483 at 110 °C (versus $5.4\text{-}7.1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ over Pd(x)/HAP catalysts). This comparison proves
484 that the HAP appears as a good alternative to the alumina support. Table 1 also lists the
485 textural properties of the assayed catalysts in the COTOX reaction. The results show
486 that no significant changes are observed in their specific surface areas and in their mean
487 pore size after two reaction cycles. Similar results were reported by Shen et al. [45] in
488 their study on the activity of Pd catalysts supported on phosphorous modified alumina
489 support. They found that the interaction between Pd clusters and P-O-Al units in the P-
490 doped Al₂O₃ prevents the sintering of Pd and the phase segregation of AlPO₄ in γ -
491 Al₂O₃.
492 On the other hand, the apparent activation energies values, obtained from Arrhenius
493 plots, are almost similar (59-60 kJ mol⁻¹) suggesting that irrespective of the used Pd
494 catalyst the CO oxidation reaction occurs through the same mechanism (Table 4). Note

495 that the obtained values are in good agreement with a number of earlier studies dealing
496 with the oxidation of CO over Pd catalysts [30,46].

497 In order to examine the stability of the prepared Pd(x)/HAP samples catalytic runs were
498 conducted at 175 °C for a considerably prolonged reaction time interval (6 h) (Fig. 8b).
499 As expected, the Pd(0.5)/HAP sample exhibits the highest initial conversion value
500 (33%) compared to 15% for Pd(1)/HAP and 9% for Pd(2)/HAP. However, CO
501 conversion over the former rapidly decreases during the first 2 h after which it tends to
502 reach a stationary state corresponding to a conversion of 19%. By contrast, over the
503 Pd(1)/HAP and Pd(2)/HAP catalysts lower rates of deactivation are observed. The
504 difference in the deactivation rate between the catalysts can be attributed to the capacity
505 of each one to strongly adsorb CO. Our CO-TPD study, discussed above, highlights the
506 presence of extra sites, which adsorb strongly the CO molecules, on the Pd(0.5)/HAP
507 catalyst surface. This may explain the high rate of deactivation observed on this catalyst
508 due to the blockage of the active sites by CO.

509 Given the promising behavior of Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst additional experiments were
510 performed to obtain a simple power law that describes the kinetics of the CO oxidation.
511 The reaction rates were determined at 160 °C for low CO conversions, which
512 corresponds to differential reactor conditions, and ensuring stable activity of the
513 catalyst. Fig. S2(a) and Fig. S2(b) (supporting information) show the effect of CO and
514 O₂ partial pressures, respectively, on the CO oxidation reaction rate. The latter seems to
515 increase monotonically with O₂ partial pressure while it decreases with CO partial
516 pressure; so a negative order with respect to CO is expected. Furthermore, logarithmic
517 plot showing the dependence of the reaction rate on the CO and O₂ partial pressures are
518 displayed in Fig. 9a and Fig. 9b, respectively. The analysis of the obtained results shows
519 that the reaction order of CO and O₂ are -0.30 and 0.46, respectively. These kinetic data

520 are consistent with those reported by Satsuma et al. [47] over Pd/Al₂O₃, Pd/ZrO₂ and
521 Pd/SiO₂ catalysts. So, they proposed Langmuir-Hinshelwood mechanism involving a
522 dissociation of oxygen molecule on the metal surface. They attributed, moreover, the
523 negative order respect to CO to self-poisoning of Pd surface by strongly adsorbed CO at
524 low temperatures.

525

526 **3.2.2. Activity in COPROX**

527 **Fig. 10a and Fig. 10b** show the curves corresponding to the CO conversion and the
528 selectivity to the CO₂ formation, in the COPROX reaction, over the Pd(x)/HAP
529 catalysts. Note that carbon dioxide is the unique carbonaceous product detected (no
530 formation of CH₄ is observed). **Table 5** lists the temperatures corresponding to a
531 conversion of 10%, the TOF determined at 175 °C and the activation energy values in
532 the temperature range 100-175 °C.

533 As shown in **Fig. 10** two temperature regions could be discussed in the activity profiles:
534 at low temperatures (≤ 275 °C) X_{CO} increases with temperature to achieve 24% at 275
535 °C and a selectivity around 12%. When compared to their activity in the COTOX
536 reaction the activity in the COPROX appears to be strongly influenced by the presence
537 of H₂ in the gas mixture. For instance, at 100 °C, under the COPROX reactants gas
538 mixture, X_{CO} reaches 6% on the Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst while it is negligible in the
539 COTOX reaction. Therefore, the enhanced low temperature reaction activity (75 °C $\leq T$
540 < 150 °C) could be attributed to the presence of H₂ which promotes the initiation of the
541 CO oxidation. This promotional effect of H₂ on CO oxidation was reported in several
542 studies dealing with the activity of noble metals catalysts in the COPROX reaction [48-
543 50].

544 By contrast, at high temperatures both X_{CO} and S_{CO_2} decrease with the reaction
545 temperature suggesting the main occurrence of the H_2 oxidation at the expense of the
546 CO oxidation. These results are in good agreement with earlier studies dealing with the
547 activity of Pd supported catalysts in COPROX [51-52]. They explained the low activity
548 at higher temperature to the presence of hydrogen which is preferentially adsorbed and
549 easily oxidised, rather than CO, on metallic Pd. Moreover, as reported in Table 1, the
550 characterization of Pd(x)/HAP post-reaction catalysts by N_2 physisorption techniques
551 shows an apparent drop in their specific surface areas (about 31-35%). These results
552 were, however, expected in the presence of very high concentration of H_2 (60%) and
553 water vapor as a product of its oxidation [54]. Nevertheless, CO conversion over the
554 Pd(x)/HAP catalysts exceeds significantly that obtained over 1% Pd/CeO₂ catalyst used
555 in the same O₂ excess conditions ($\lambda=2$). The CO conversion on the latter, previously
556 reported by Pozdnyakova et al. [51], did not reach 12% even at 300 °C (versus 17-24%
557 reached over our Pd(x)/HAP catalysts). The performance of our Pd supported catalysts
558 is also compared with that of 1%Pd/Ce_{0.63}Zr_{0.37}O₂ catalysts reported by Mariño et al.
559 [53]. The latter obtained lower values in terms of CO conversions (< 10%) and
560 selectivity (< 15%) in all the investigated temperature range (50-250 °C). This
561 comparison shows a clear catalytic performance superiority of our Pd(x)/HAP catalysts.
562 The TOF values determined at 175 °C are included in Table 5. Over the Pd(0.5)/HAP
563 and Pd(1)/HAP catalysts the TOF are about $110 \times 10^{-3} s^{-1}$ whereas the lowest value ($84 \times$
564 $10^{-3} s^{-1}$) is obtained on the Pd(2)/HAP catalyst. The difference between the Pd(x)/HAP
565 catalysts is probably related to the distribution of the active palladium species. The
566 superior activity of the Pd(0.5)/HAP and Pd(1)/HAP samples suggests that they possess
567 more efficient palladium sites than those deposited on Pd(2)/HAP catalyst. According to
568 the TEM and H_2 chemisorption results on the latter larger Pd particles are deposited

569 which also makes it less active and stable, at 175 °C, during 6 h on stream (Fig. 10c).
570 The activation energy values on the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts are also listed in Table 5.
571 These values, 16.5-26.4 kJ mol⁻¹, are considered very low when compared to those
572 obtained in the COTOX reaction (about 60 kJ mol⁻¹). Hence, this overall activation
573 energy barrier lowering is consistent with the above-mentioned proposal which points
574 out the promotional effect of H₂ on the CO oxidation reaction.

575

576 **3.2.3. Activity in WGS reaction**

577 The performance and the stability of the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts were also studied in the
578 WGS reaction. The catalysts were submitted to the same pre-treatment routine realized
579 before the COTOX and the COPROX experiments (reduction at 200 °C). Fig. 11a and
580 Fig. 11b show the light-off curves and the CO conversion as function of time on stream
581 (at 275 °C), respectively.

582 On all the assayed Pd(x)/HAP samples CO activation starts around 150 °C after which,
583 depending on the Pd loading, the conversion increases with the reaction temperature via
584 different pathways (Fig. 11a). For instance, the Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst exhibits the lowest
585 temperature required to reach a conversion of 10% (300 °C) whereas higher
586 temperatures are needed in the case of Pd(1)/HAP and Pd(2)/HAP catalysts (345 °C and
587 385 °C, respectively). Likewise, the catalyst with the highest palladium loading (2%)
588 exhibits the poorest performance at 400 °C with a conversion lower than 12%. This may
589 be associated to the low dispersion of Pd and, then, the low density of the metal-support
590 interface sites required for the WGS reaction [22]. However, the Pd(0.5)/HAP sample
591 proves the best catalytic performance at 400 °C with a conversion reaching 26%. As
592 discussed above, it is probably the metal-support interaction features that make of the
593 hydroxyapatite such interesting carrier. For instance, in their study on the WGS reaction

594 over Pd/Al₂O₃ catalysts, Lupescu et al. [22] found a conversion below 11% at 400 °C.
595 They attributed the poor activity of their catalysts to the lack of oxygen mobility in the
596 support material. On another hand, the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts demonstrate good
597 resistance against surface area loss (Table 1).

598 Fig. 11b displays the activity of the Pd(x)/HAP as a function of time on stream at 275
599 °C. A comparison of the initial conversion shows that the Pd(0.5)/HAP sample presents
600 the highest value (9%) compared to 5% for Pd(1)/HAP and 6% for Pd(2)/HAP.
601 However, on all the assayed catalysts, CO conversion presents an apparent instability
602 during the first 1 h. After this instability period the activity stays almost constant
603 corresponding to a conversion of 7% for Pd(0.5)/HAP, 4% for Pd(1)/HAP and 3% for
604 Pd(2)/HAP catalyst.

605 Table 5 also lists the specific catalytic activity (TOF, at 275 °C) and the activation
606 energy values for the three Pd(x)/HAP catalysts. A comparison of the apparent E_a for
607 the assayed samples, 44.3-59.7 kJ mol⁻¹, to those reported in the literature shows that
608 they are quite similar [22]. The TOF values seem to follow similar tendency compared
609 to that observed in COTOX and COPROX reactions. Indeed, TOF decreases from 47 ×
610 10⁻³ s⁻¹ over Pd(0.5)/HAP to 22 × 10⁻³ s⁻¹ for Pd(2)/HAP. It is admitted that the activity
611 in WGS reaction is related to the reducibility and the oxygen storage capacity of the
612 catalyst [22]. In this sense, the high performance of our Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst could be
613 explained by the presence of small Pd particle sizes that present higher reducibility and
614 higher oxygen storage capacity.

615

616 4. Conclusion

617 Pd(x)/hydroxyapatite catalysts (0.5 ≤ x ≤ 2) have been synthesized and characterized by
618 a wide number of analytical techniques including N₂ physisorption, XRD, H₂-TPR, H₂

619 chemisorption, TEM, CO-TPD, OSCC and OSC techniques. The characterisation
620 results show the presence of a fraction representing 0.3 wt.% Pd which has been
621 incorporated into the hydroxyapatite network and the deposition of Pd species spread as
622 metallic Pd over the carrier. The chemical and physical properties of the latter are
623 affected by the Pd content. Due to its smaller Pd particle sizes the Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst
624 demonstrates stronger CO adsorption, higher reducibility in the presence of CO and
625 higher oxygen mobility compared to the high loading samples (1% and 2%). These
626 interesting features seem to contribute in the enhancement of the activity and selectivity
627 in the three investigated CO elimination processes (COTOX, COPROX and WGS). By
628 contrast, despite exhibiting similar active Pd surface area, compared to those measured
629 on Pd(0.5)/HAP and Pd(1)/HAP, the Pd-rich catalyst (2%) exhibits the poorest
630 performance. This finding points out that over Pd(x)/HAP catalysts the CO oxidation
631 via the three processes is a structure-sensitive catalytic reaction where the distribution of
632 the Pd species plays a key role in their performance. Moreover, the performances of the
633 Pd/HAP catalysts evidence the potential of HAP support as promising alternative to
634 those reported in the available literature.

635 Work is in progress toward improving the activity and selectivity of Pd(x)/HAP
636 catalysts through the use of promoters.

637

638 **5. Acknowledgements**

639 The financial support for this work provided by Gobierno Vasco (GIC IT-657-13) and
640 Ministerio de Economía y Competitividad (ENE2013-41187-R) is gratefully
641 acknowledged. Likewise, the technical support provided by SGIker (UPV/EHU) is
642 gratefully acknowledged.

643

644 **6. References**

- 645 [1] K. Liu, A. Wang, T. Zhang, *ACS Catal.* 2 (2012) 1165-1178.
- 646 [2] Z. Boukha, J.L. Ayastuy, A. Iglesias-González, B. Pereda-Ayo, M.A. Gutiérrez-
647 Ortiz, J.R. González-Velasco, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 40 (2015) 7318-7328.
- 648 [3] Z. Boukha, J.L. Ayastuy, A. Iglesias-González, B. Pereda-Ayo, M.A. Gutiérrez-
649 Ortiz, J.R. González-Velasco, *Appl. Catal. B* 160-161 (2014) 629-640.
- 650 [4] N.K. Gamboa-Rosales, J.L. Ayastuy, Z. Boukha, N. Bion, D. Duprez, J.A. Pérez-
651 Omil, E. del Río, M.A. Gutiérrez-Ortiz, *Appl. Catal. B* 168–169 (2015) 87-97.
- 652 [5] Y. Zhou, Z. Wang, C. Liu, *Catal. Sci. Technol.* 5 (2015) 69-81.
- 653 [6] A. Satsuma, K. Osaki, M. Yanagihara, J. Ohyama, K. Shimizu, *Appl. Catal. B* 132-
654 133 (2013) 511-518
- 655 [7] H. Zhu, Z. Qin, W. Shan, W. Shen, J. Wang, *J. Catal.* 225 (2004) 267-277.
- 656 [8] L. Liu, F. Zhou, L. Wang, X. Qi, F. Shi, Y. Deng, *J. Catal.* 274 (2010) 1-10.
- 657 [9] D.I. Kochubey, S.N. Pavlova, B.N. Novgorodov, G.N. Kryukova, V.A. Sadykov, *J.*
658 *Catal.* 161 (1996) 500-506.
- 659 [10] Y. Li, Y. Yu, J.-. Wang, J. Song, Q. Li, M. Dong, C.-. Liu, *Appl. Catal. B* 125
660 (2012) 189-196.
- 661 [11] K. Tanikawa, C. Egawa, *Appl. Catal. A* 403 (2011) 12-17.
- 662 [12] R.S. Johnson, A. DeLaRiva, V. Ashbacher, B. Halevi, C.J. Villanueva, G.K. Smith,
663 S. Lin, A.K. Datye, H. Guo, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 15 (2013) 7768-7776.
- 664 [13] Y. Zhou, Z. Wang, C. Liu, *Catal. Sci. Technol.* 5 (2015) 69-81.
- 665 [14] M. Haneda, M. Todo, Y. Nakamura, M. Hattori, *Catal. Today* doi:
666 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2016.05.025>.
- 667 [15] S.H. Oh, R.M. Sinkevitch, *J. Catal.* 142 (1993) 254.

668 [16] O. Pozdnyakova, D. Teschner, A. Wootsch, J. Kröhnert, B. Steinhauer, H. Sauer,
669 L. Toth, F.C. Jentoft, A. Knop-Gericke, Z. Paál, R. Schlögl, *J. Catal.* 237 (2006) 17-28.
670 [17] F. Marino, C. Descorme, D. Duprez, *Appl. Catal. B* 54 (2004) 59-66.
671 [18] Y. Sekine, T. Chihara, R. Watanabe, Y. Sakamoto, M. Matsukata, E. Kikuchi,
672 *Catal. Lett.* 140 (2010) 184-188.
673 [19] Y. Sekine, H. Takamatsu, S. Aramaki, K. Ichishima, M. Takada, M. Matsukata, E.
674 Kikuchi, *Appl. Catal. A* 352 (2009) 214-222.
675 [20] S. Hilaire, X. Wang, T. Luo, R.J. Gorte, J. Wagner, *Appl. Catal. A* 215 (2001) 271-
676 278.
677 [21] T. Bunluesin, R.J. Gorte, G.W. Graham, *Appl. Catal. B* 15 (1998) 107-114.
678 [22] J.A. Lupescu, J.W. Schwank, K.A. Dahlberg, C.Y. Seo, G.B. Fisher, S.L.
679 Peczonczyk, K. Rhodes, M.J. Jagner, L.P. Haack, *Appl. Catal. B* 183 (2016) 343-360.
680 [23] J.A. Lupescu, J.W. Schwank, G.B. Fisher, X. Chen, S.L. Peczonczyk, A.R. Drews,
681 *Appl. Catal. B* 185 (2016) 189-202.
682 [24] Z. Boukha, J. González-Prior, B.d. Rivas, J.R. González-Velasco, R. López-
683 Fonseca, J.I. Gutiérrez-Ortiz, *Appl. Catal. B* 190 (2016) 125-136.
684 [25] Z. Boukha, M. Kacimi, M.F.R. Pereira, J.L. Faria, J.L. Figueiredo, M. Ziyad, *Appl.*
685 *Catal. A* 317 (2007) 299-309.
686 [26] Z. Boukha, M. Kacimi, M. Ziyad, A. Ensuque, F. Bozon-Verduraz, *J. Mol. Catal.*
687 *A* 270 (2007) 205-213.
688 [27] A. Borodzinski, M. Bonarowska, *Langmuir* 13 (1997) 5613-5620.
689 [28] M.A. Aramendia, V. Borau, C. Jimenez, J.M. Marinas, A. Moreno, *Colloid.*
690 *Surface. A* 106 (1996) 161-165
691 [29] J.L. Ayastuy, A. Gurbani, M.P. González-Marcos, M.A. Gutiérrez-Ortiz, *Ind. Eng.*
692 *Chem. Res.* 48 (2009) 5633-5641.

693 [30] J.R. Gaudet, A. de la Riva, E.J. Peterson, T. Bolin, A.K. Datye, *ACS Catal.* 3 (5)
694 (2013) 846-855.

695 [31] J. Panpranot, O. Tangjitwattakorn, P. Praserthdam, J.G. Goodwin, *Appl. Catal. A*
696 292 (2005) 322-327.

697 [32] W.J. Shen, M. Okumura, Y. Matsumura, M. Haruta, *Appl. Catal. A* 213 (2001)
698 225-232.

699 [33] G. Neri, M.G. Musolino, C. Milone, D. Pietropaolo, S. Glavagno, *Appl. Catal. A*
700 208 (2001) 307-316.

701 [34] J. Wang, H. Chen, Z. Hu, M. Yao, Y. Li, *Catal. Rev. Sci. Eng.* 57 (2015) 79-144.

702 [35] F.B. Noronha, M.A.S. Baldanza, M. Schmal, *J. Catal.* 188 (1999) 270-280.

703 [36] J.S. Rieck, A.T. Bell, *J. Catal.* 96 (1985) 88-105.

704 [37] J.S. Rieck, A.T. Bell, *J. Catal.* 103 (1987) 46-54.

705 [38] L. Pastor-Pérez, T.R. Reina, S. Ivanova, M.A. Centeno, J.A. Odriozola, A.
706 Sepúlveda-Escribano, *Catalysts* 5 (2015) 298-309.

707 [39] S. Bedrane, C. Descorme, D. Duprez, *Catal. Today* 73 (2002) 233-238.

708 [40] T.R. Reina, S. Ivanova, J.J. Delgado, I. Ivanov, V. Idakiev, T. Tabakova, M.A.
709 Centeno, J.A. Odriozola, *ChemCatChem* 6 (2014) 1401-1409.

710 [41] M. Jin, J. Park, J.K. Shon, J.H. Kim, Z. Li, Y. Park, J.M. Kim, *Catal. Today* 185
711 (2012) 183-190.

712 [42] T.R. Reina, S. Ivanova, M.A. Centeno, J.A. Odriozola, *Front. Chem.* 12 (2013) 1-9.

713 [43] X. Liu, R. Wang, L. Song, H. He, G. Zhang, X. Zi, W. Qiu, *Catal. Commun.* 46
714 (2014) 213-218.

715 [44] M. Jin, H. Liu, H. Zhang, Z. Xie, J. Liu, Y. Xia, *Nano. Res.* 4 (2011) 83-91.

716 [45] M. Shen, L. Song, J. Wang, X. Wang, *Catal. Commun.* 22 (2012) 28-33.

717 [46] Y. Li, Y. Yu, J. Wang, J. Song, Q. Li, M. Dong, C. Liu, *Appl. Catal. B* 125 (2012)
718 189-196.

719 [47] A. Satsuma, K. Osaki, M. Yanagihara, J. Ohyama, K. Shimizu, *Appl. Catal. B* 132-
720 133 (2013) 511-518.

721 [48] T. Nguyen, F. Morfin, M. Aouine, F. Bosselet, J. Rousset, L. Piccolo, *Catal. Today*
722 253 (2015) 106-114.

723 [49] S. Salomons, R.E. Hayes, M. Votsmeier, *Appl. Catal. A* 352 (2009) 27-34.

724 [50] M.J. Kahlich, H.A. Gasteiger, R.J. Behm, *J. Catal.* 171 (1997) 93-105.

725 [51] O. Pozdnyakova, D. Teschner, A. Wootsch, J. Kröhnert, B. Steinhauer, H. Sauer,
726 L. Toth, F.C. Jentoft, A. Knop-Gericke, Z. Paál, R. Schlögl, *J. Catal.* 237 (2006) 17-28.

727 [52] M. Navlani-García, I. Miguel-García, A. Berenguer-Murcia, D. Lozano-Castelló,
728 D. Cazorla-Amorósa and H. Yamashita, *Catal. Sci. Technol.* 6 (2016) 2623.

729 [53] F. Mariño, C. Descorme, D. Duprez, *Appl. Catal. B* 54 (2004) 59.

730 [54] C.H. Bartholomew, *Appl. Catal. A* 212 (2001) 17-60.

731

732

733

734

735

736

737

738

739

740

741

742 CAPTIONS FOR TABLES AND FIGURES

- Table 1 Chemical composition and textural properties of the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts (calcined, reduced and used in COTOX, COPROX and WGR reactions).
- Table 2 XRD and TEM data for the reduced Pd(x)/HAP catalysts.
- Table 3 H₂-TPR, H₂ chemisorptions and CO-TPD data for the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts.
- Table 4 Activity data of Pd(x)/HAP catalysts in the COTOX reaction.
- Table 5 Activity data of Pd(x)/HAP catalysts in the COPROX and WGS reactions.
- Fig. 1 (a) XRD patterns of the reduced Pd(x)/HAP catalysts and (b) their magnification in the 2θ angles range of 30°-37°.
- Fig. 2 TEM micrographs of the reduced Pd(x)/HAP catalysts.
- Fig. 3 H₂-TPR profiles of the Pd(x)/HAP catalysts.
- Fig. 4 Pd particle size, determined by (a) TEM and (b) H₂ chemisorption, dependence on the H₂(II)/Pd molar ratio (determined by H₂-TPR).
- Fig. 5 TPD-MS study of CO pre-adsorbed on Pd(x)/HAP: spectra corresponding to the (a) m/z=28 and (b) m/z=44 signals
- Fig. 6 Evolution of (a) OSCC and (b) OSC as a function of temperature over HAP bare support and Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst.
- Fig. 7 Evolution of (a) OSCC and (b) OSC as a function of temperature over Pd(x)/HAP catalysts.
- Fig. 8 CO oxidation over Pd(x)/HAP catalysts: (a) Light-off curves and (b) CO conversion at 175 °C as a function of time on stream
- Fig. 9 Logarithmic plot of reaction rate at 160 °C vs partial pressure of (a) CO and (b) O₂ over Pd(0.5)/HAP catalyst.

Fig. 10 Activity of the Pd(x)HAP catalysts in COPROX: (a) CO conversion, (b) selectivity to CO₂ and (c) CO conversion at 175 °C as a function of time on stream

Fig. 11 WGS reaction over Pd(x)/HAP catalysts: (a) Light-off curves and (b) CO conversion at 275 °C as a function of time on stream

743

Catalysts	Pd, wt. %		$S_{\text{BET}}, \text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$	Pore volume, $\text{cm}^3 \text{g}^{-1}$	Pore size, nm
HAP	0.00 (1.50)	Calcined	52.0	0.45	30.3
Pd(0.5)/HAP	0.56 (1.51)	Calcined	48.0	0.39	28.0
		Reduced	44.0	0.37	31.3
		COTOX	45.0	0.39	28.7
		COPROX	29.0	0.32	28.3
		WGS	46.0	0.39	28.3
Pd(1)/HAP	0.99 (1.52)	Calcined	48.0	0.40	30.0
		Reduced	44.0	0.38	30.8
		COTOX	43.0	0.32	27.8
		COPROX	30.0	0.32	30.4
		WGS	46.0	0.41	29.4
Pd(2)/HAP	2.05 (1.53)	Calcined	48.0	0.37	29.0
		Reduced	42.0	0.35	30.5
		COTOX	44.0	0.35	26.6
		COPROX	27.0	0.30	27.0
		WGS	44.0	0.39	28.6

Values in brackets correspond to (Ca+Pd)/P molar ratios.

Table 1

744
745
746

747

748

749

Catalysts	XRD			TEM		
	(a±0.01), Å	(c±0.002), Å	V, Å ³	D _{TEM} , %	d, nm	S _{Pd} , m ² /g _{cat}
HAP	9.3414	6.8198	515.4	-	-	-
HAP (1.67) ^(*)	9.4154	6.8792	528.1	-	-	-
Pd(0.5)/HAP	9.3713	6.8438	520.5	19.0	7.6	0.45
Pd(1)/HAP	9.3802	6.8418	521.3	10.4	13.1	0.49
Pd(2)/HAP	9.3941	6.8319	522.1	8.4	16.3	0.79

^(*) Values extracted from “JCPDS 01-082-2956” reference card.

750

751

752

Table 2

753

754

755

756

757

758

759

Catalysts	H ₂ -TPR					H ₂ chemisorption			CO-TPD	
	Peak I ^(a) μmol g ⁻¹	Peak II ^(b) μmol g ⁻¹	H ₂ (I)/Pd	H ₂ (II)/Pd	H ₂ ^(R) /Pd ^(c)	D _{chem} , %	d, nm	S _{Pd} , m ² /g _{cat}	CO, μmol g ⁻¹	CO ₂ , μmol g ⁻¹
Pd(0.5)/HAP	23.3	3.4	0.5	0.07	0.43	21.3	5.6	0.46	182	4.0
Pd(1)/HAP	77.0	10.2	0.8	0.11	0.69	9.2	15.3	0.42	215	2.7
Pd(2)/HAP	182.0	29.0	1.0	0.15	0.85	5.0	28.1	0.44	230	2.9

760

761

(a) Total amounts of H₂ consumed at 22 °C.

762

(b) Amounts of released H₂ at 68 °C.

763

(c) Data corresponding to actual amounts of consumed H₂ for the reduction process (H₂^(R)/Pd= H₂(I)/Pd - H₂(II)/Pd).

764

765

766

767

Table 3

768

769

770
771
772
773
774
775
776

Catalysts	T ₅₀ , °C	TOF ₁₁₀ (× 10 ³ s ⁻¹)	TOF ₁₄₀ (× 10 ³ s ⁻¹)	TOF ₁₇₅ (× 10 ³ s ⁻¹)	E _a , kJ mol ⁻¹ (125-175°C)
Pd(0.5)/HAP	204	7.1	36.6	133.8	62.3
Pd(1)/HAP	207	5.4	31.1	113.0	61.9
Pd(2)/HAP	209	6.5	21.0	67.2	59.8

777
778
779
780
781
782
783
784
785
786
787
788
789
790
791
792

Table 4

793
794
795
796

Catalysts	COPROX			WGS		
	T ₁₀ , °C	TOF ₁₇₅ (× 10 ³ s ⁻¹)	E _a , kJ mol ⁻¹ (125-175°C)	T ₁₀ , °C	TOF ₂₇₅ (× 10 ³ s ⁻¹)	E _a , kJ mol ⁻¹ (225-325°C)
Pd(0.5)/HAP	160	110	19.7	300	47.3	56.3
Pd(1)/HAP	177	112	16.5	345	40.0	44.3
Pd(2)/HAP	187	84	26.4	385	21.8	59.7

797
798
799
800
801
802
803
804
805
806
807
808
809
810
811
812
813
814

Table 5

815

816

817

818

819

820

Figure 1

821

822

823

824

825

Figure 2

828

829

830

831

832

833

Figure 3

Figure 4

835

836

837

838

839

840

841

842

Figure 5

843

844

845

846

Figure 6

847

848

849

850

Figure 7

851

852

853

Figure 8

854

855

856

857

Figure 9

858

859

860

861

862

Figure 10

863

864

865

866

867

Figure 11